

GAME-ER

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D3.2

Meeting minutes and preliminary comparative results

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10	GAME ONLY	GO	France
11	HERNÍ KLASTR Z.S.	HK	Czechia
12	MUNICIPIO DO FUNDAO	CMF	Portugal
13	THE UNIVERSITY COURT OF ABERTAY UNIVERSITY	AU	United Kingdom

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GLOSSARY AND ABBREVIATIONS

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AVMS	Audiovisual Media Services
BM	Bi-monthly meeting
CCI	Cultural and Creative Industries
CR	Compte-rendu (meeting minutes)
CRG	Centre de Recherche en Gestion (École Polytechnique – i3)
D	Deliverable
DMA	DMA Design (Dundee game studio, creator of Lemmings and GTA)
DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ENJMIN	École Nationale du Jeu et des Médias Interactifs Numériques (Angoulême)
GA	Grant Agreement
GDA	Game Developers Association
IGDA	International Game Developers Association
IIDEA	Italian Interactive Digital Entertainment Association
IP	Intellectual Property
JIC	South Moravian Innovation Agency (Jihomoravské inovační centrum)
MobyGames	MobyGames (online video game database used for WP2 mapping)
OGR	Officine Grandi Riparazioni (Turin)
QCA	Qualitative Comparative Analysis
SNJV	Syndicat National du Jeu Vidéo (France)
SoGames	SoGames (Bordeaux video game cluster association)
T	Task
UBI	Universidade da Beira Interior
VGI	Video Game Industry
WP	Work Package
WS	Working Session

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the work conducted under **Task 3.2 (T3.2) – Facilitation of the case study steering committee** – of the **GAME-ER** project. Within **Work Package 3 (WP3)**, which is dedicated to the cross-case comparative analysis and the construction of a typology of European video game clusters, deliverable **D3.2** is the bridge between **D3.1**, which delivered the consolidated analytical grid, and **D3.3**, which will deliver the comparative analysis and the typology itself. **D3.2** documents how the analytical grid has been put into practice across the six **GAME-ER** clusters – Dundee (Scotland), Turin (Italy), Brno (Czechia), Fundão (Portugal), Lyon and Bordeaux (France) – what methodological refinements emerged from this confrontation with the field, and how the comparative framework progressively crystallised into a workable approach for the typology to come.

The empirical material of this deliverable is the case study steering committee itself, manifested through **seven bi-monthly meetings and two methodological working sessions held between December 2024 and May 2026**. In each bi-monthly meeting, one cluster team presented its case through a narrative reconstruction of the cluster’s history and a shared codebook and confronted its findings with the WP3 analytical grid; project partners then identified resonances and divergences with their own cases. This format allowed the grid to move from a paper artefact to a living analytical practice, tested across six clusters working in five languages and several disciplinary traditions. The report documents three main contributions.

- First, it traces the **progressive refinement of the analytical toolkit**: a sequence of conceptual shifts and refinements – the static/processual distinction, the organisation/organising distinction, the unpacking of “membership” into territorial presence, collaboration involvement and sense of belonging, and the integration of proximity grids – together with the coding strategies and tools deployed across teams (NVivo, AI-assisted and manual coding).
- Second, it sets out the **methodological architecture adopted for D3.3**: a causality-based approach that identifies recurring micro-mechanisms and configurational causalities rather than statistical regularities and articulates the regional-level WP2 spatial analysis with the cluster-level WP4 case studies through a triangulation logic.
- Third, it consolidates a set of **cross-cutting observations** emerging from the meetings which inform, without pre-empting, the typology construction. These observations include:
 - five convergent patterns (the centrality of informal networks; the role of tertiary education; the tension between artistic and business logics; crises as catalysts for collective action; and the demand for political recognition)
 - four discriminating dimensions (trajectory of emergence, degree of formalisation, presence of an anchor firm or institution, and articulation with the national context).

The report closes by formalising the handover to D3.3, specifying the six-phase production process, the allocation of thematic leadership among partners, and the calendar. In doing so, D3.2 serves both as the operational record of the facilitation work conducted under T3.2 and as the launching document for the comparative analysis and typology of European video game clusters.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Project Overview

The Gaming Clusters Across Multiple European Regions (**GAME-ER**) project aims to explore the emergence, development, and sustainability of video game clusters, with a specific focus on local and regional clusters. The project will develop a comprehensive Interactive Methodological Toolkit, featuring policy and practical recommendations designed to assist local and national policymakers in establishing or enhancing Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) clusters within their regions or cities. Existing research often focuses on clusters outside Europe or within major metropolitan areas like Helsinki or Hamburg. However, **GAME-ER** addresses a critical gap by studying the dynamics of smaller, regional clusters, which play a significant role in driving innovation, growth, and regional cohesion. The project's core component involves a comparative analysis of six clusters in five European countries—France, the Czech Republic, Italy, Scotland, and Portugal. These clusters were chosen for their diverse levels of maturity and unique characteristics, including concentrations of creative talent and companies. In addition to this comparative study, **GAME-ER** will conduct a Europe-wide analysis of the spatial organization of the video games industry, specifically focusing on local and regional ecosystems. This research, conducted in collaboration with policymakers and industry stakeholders, will guide the formulation of actionable recommendations using a participatory approach. **GAME-ER** brings together 15 partners from 9 countries, encompassing expertise in social sciences, humanities, policymaking, business, and innovation.

1.2. Objectives of the deliverable

D3.2 aims to document the operational and methodological work carried out within **T3.2**, which bridges the construction of the analytical framework (**D3.1**) and the forthcoming comparative analysis and typology (**D3.3**). Building on the analytical grid delivered in **D3.1**, **T3.2** both animated the case study steering committee across seven bi-monthly meetings and two methodological working sessions, and progressively refined the comparative framework in direct dialogue with the empirical outputs of **WP4 (D4.1, D4.2, D4.3)** and the spatial analysis of **WP2 (D2.2, D2.3)**.

The goals of the deliverable are thus twofold:

- First, it aims to document how the analytical grid developed in **D3.1** was operationalised across six case studies, what methodological refinements emerged from its confrontation with the field, and how the case study steering committee was designed and animated to produce a shared and workable comparative toolkit.
- Second, by tracking the cross-cutting observations and discriminating dimensions that emerged from the seven bi-monthly meetings, it seeks to establish the analytical foundations (without pre-empting the conclusions) upon which **D3.3** will construct the cross-cluster typology and the final comparative analysis.

1.3. Deliverable structure

The deliverable is organised in five sections plus the introduction and the annexes.

- **Section 2** presents the case study steering committee: its rationale, its operating logic, its calendar, and its articulation with the rest of the project.
- **Section 3** is the core analytical section of the deliverable. It documents how the toolkit was progressively built and refined through **T3.2**: how the **D3.1** grid was tested, what conceptual moves shaped its maturation, what coding strategies and analytical tools were deployed across teams, and how the methodological architecture for **D3.3** (a causality-based approach articulated with the WP2 spatial analysis) was finalised.
- **Section 4** consolidates the cross-cutting observations that emerged across the meetings: convergent patterns and discriminating dimensions identified across cases. It remains at the descriptive level – the analytical synthesis is reserved for **D3.3**.
- **Section 5** documents the handover to **D3.3**: the methodological architecture decided for the comparative analysis and typology, the six-phase process, the labour division among partners, the calendar, and the articulation with **D3.3**.
- **Section 6** concludes and opens onto the next deliverables.

Annex A provides a structured synthesis of each of the seven bi-monthly meetings and of the two methodological working sessions, in a common “meeting minutes” format. These syntheses focus on what was learned about the methodology and the comparative framework – they are not cluster reports (cluster reports are in WP4 deliverables).

The deliverable can be read in two ways. A **synthetic reading** follows Sections 1, 2, 3.1, 4, 5 and 6, providing the essential storyline of **T3.2** and the preparation of **D3.3**. A **detailed reading** adds Section 3 (full) and **Annex A**, providing the granular methodological reasoning and the meeting-by-meeting trace.

To structure the narrative, the deliverable is articulated around **three key stages** of the T3.2 facilitation work, which emerged inductively from the bi-monthly meeting sequence:

- **Key Stage 1 – Refining the grid through the first meetings;**
- **Key Stage 2 – Testing the grid on each case study** (one meeting for each case study);
- **Key Stage 3 – Initiating the comparative dialogue and operationalising the transition to D3.3;**

These three stages are referenced consistently throughout the document.

2. CASE STUDY STEERING COMMITTEE. RATIONALE, FORMAT AND OPERATIONAL STRUCTURE

The construction of an empirically grounded typology of European video game clusters requires assembling, in a comparable form, the outputs of six independent case studies conducted by six different teams, based in five countries, working in five different languages, drawing on partly distinct disciplinary backgrounds (game studies, sociology of organisations, economic geography, management research, regional economics), and confronting six clusters with markedly different histories, sizes, and degrees of institutional formalisation. The **T3.2** was designed with the aim of allowing the following functions:

- **enable each partner to develop a shared understanding of the other case studies**, beyond what can be conveyed through written deliverables alone;
- **test the WP3 analytical grid on the field**, gather feedback on its strengths and limitations, and progressively refine it into an operational comparative framework;
- **prepare the cross-cluster comparative work** by initiating, well before the formal start of **T3.3**, a comparative dialogue between teams.

In practical terms, **T3.2** is the place where the grid moves from a paper artefact (its form in **D3.1**) to a living analytical practice – and where the conditions for the typology construction (**D3.3**) are progressively assembled.

One specific challenge of the project deserves to be mentioned, because it has shaped a substantial part of the methodological discussions held during the bi-monthly meetings. The very term *cluster* – central to the grant agreement and to the project’s communication – has been **resisted, qualified, or reframed** by interviewees in almost every case study. In Turin, respondents preferred *ecosystem, network* or *scene*. In Dundee, the term is barely used by local actors. In Brno, the existence of a formal organisation called *Game Cluster* generated a constant terminological ambiguity between the research object and the local association. The case study steering committee was the venue where these terminological discussions were progressively pooled and where shared analytical conventions could be elaborated. For reference in this deliverable, **Table 1** presents the six clusters studied, lead teams and related tasks coordinated which relates to the WP3 work:

Table 1 GAME-ER clusters and relation with WP3

Cluster	Region	Lead team	Other WP3-relevant tasks led
Dundee	Eastern Scotland, UK	AU University	T4.2 actor mapping, T4.5 skills and competencies
Turin	Piedmont, Italy	Università di Torino (UNITO)	T4.3 historical task, T2 spatial analysis (with Enrico Bertacchini)

Brno	South Moravia, Czech Republic	Charles University (CUNI)	T4.4 actor mapping
Fundão	Beira Interior, Portugal	INOVA+	GAME-ER general Coordination
Lyon	Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes, France	CRG – École Polytechnique	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T4.1
Bordeaux–Angoulême	Nouvelle-Aquitaine, France	CRG – École Polytechnique	T3.1, T3.2, T3.3, T4.1

Each of the six teams holds a double mission within the project.

- As **lead team for a cluster case study**, the team conducts the fieldwork (**T4.1** thematic interviews, **T4.3** historical reconstruction, **T4.4** actor mapping, **T4.5** skills survey) and produces the cluster-specific outputs that feed the WP4 deliverables.
- As **thematic leader for one of the cross-cutting WP3 dimensions**, the team produces (during **T3.3**) the comparative analysis along that dimension, based on the material provided by all the other teams.

This double mission is one of the cornerstones of the comparative architecture and is discussed in detail in Section 6. In addition, the **WP2 spatial analysis and regional mapping** (led by UNITO) produced complementary outputs at the regional level (geolocalised company mapping, regional typology of European video game clusters, longitudinal demography). The articulation between **WP2** and **WP3** is documented in Section 3.7.

2.1. The bi-Monthly Meetings format

The case study steering committee operates through **bi-monthly meetings**. The first bi-monthly meetings focused on individual presentations of each cluster and followed the same agenda:

Table 2 Bi-Monthly Meetings Format

Topic	Description
Opening/ Introduction [10 minutes]	Promoted by the facilitation team (CRG): reminder of the meeting’s objectives, recap of the previous meeting’s outputs, and introduction of the presenting team.
Cluster presentations [45-60 minutes]	Cluster presentation by the presenting team (typically 45–60 minutes), structured around:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the local context (city, region, industrial history, demographic and economic specificities); • timeline of the cluster’s emergence and evolution, identifying major phases and tipping points; • the state of the fieldwork (interviews conducted, mapping status, transcripts); • the codebook: themes, codes, sub-codes, examples; • the key findings on cluster characteristics, strengths, criticalities; • the reflection on the WP3 analytical grid: which categories proved most useful, which were less useful, which needed to be added or refined.
Q&A and cross-cluster discussion [10-20 minutes]	Structured by the facilitation team. The discussants raise comparative questions, identify convergences with their own case study, and signal divergences worth investigating further.
Closing notes [5 minutes]	Facilitation team’s synthesis, identification of follow-up actions, scheduling of the next meeting.

The narrative principle. The presenting team is invited not to present a checklist of findings against the grid, but to **tell the story of the cluster** – its emergence, its tipping points, its evolutionary dynamics. This narrative posture proved essential, because it made visible the **mechanisms and causal links** between contextual factors, actors and outcomes, which a purely categorial reading of the grid would have flattened. As discussed in Section 3, this orientation prefigured the causality-based methodology that was later formally adopted for **D3.3**.

The codebook-sharing principle. Each team shares its codebook (or its work-in-progress codebook) and its mapping of the codebook onto the **WP3** grid. This makes visible, in a direct and comparable way, what the team has chosen to code as relevant to a given dimension, where the team has had to adapt or extend the grid, and where the grid has produced gaps or redundancies. This systematic codebook-sharing is one of the most distinctive features of the **GAME-ER** facilitation work, and it is what made the cumulative refinement of the toolkit possible.

2.2. Bi-Monthly Meetings schedule

The case study steering committee held **seven bi-monthly meetings** and **two methodological working sessions** between December 2024 and May 2026. The calendar is summarised in the table below.

Table 3 Calendar of WP3 bi-monthly meetings

#	Date	Type	Focal cluster / topic	Presenting team	Key methodological output
BM #1	17 Dec 2024	Bi-monthly	Dundee	AU	First systematic feedback on the D3.1 grid; identification of useful vs less useful categories; introduction of “timeline as primary analytical tool”
BM #2	24 Feb 2025	Bi-monthly	Turin	UNITO	Second feedback on the grid; codebook with 4 themes / 27 codes / 83 sub-codes; introduction of “entry mechanisms” sub-code
WS #4	7 Mar 2025	Working session	Grid refinement	AU + UNITO + CRG	Six conceptual moves: static/processual, organisation/organising (Gherardi), three irreducible tensions (ecosystem/association, holistic/firm-level, static/longitudinal), dismantling of “membership”, introduction of “sense of belonging”, integration of Boschma’s proximity grid
BM #3	30 Apr 2025	Bi-monthly	Brno	CUNI	Codebook with 4 official goals + cluster DNA codes; identification of the cluster-as-research-object vs cluster-as-organisation ambiguity (Stefano De Paoli, Thomas Paris); audiovisual law lobbying episode
BM #4	8 Jul 2025	Bi-monthly	Fundão	INOVA+	18 themes structured in foundational / strategic / operational / socio-cultural layers; first cross-cluster comparative

					dialogue initiated by CRG; ChatGPT-assisted coding methodology and its pitfalls
BM #5	1 Oct 2025	Bi-monthly	Lyon	CRG	Six-phase historical model; “crisis as positive catalyst” as cross-cutting hypothesis; multipolar leadership (formal + emblematic individuals); triple typology of services (basic / semi-selective / very selective)
BM #6	26 Nov 2025	Bi-monthly	Bordeaux (focus on 2002–2007 transition) + D3.3 governance	CRG	Methodological transition from T3.2 to T3.3 initiated; proposed structure for D3.3; “baby deliverable” ambition; “concurrent engineering” with D3.4 recommendations
BM #7	24 Feb 2026	Bi-monthly (transversal)	D3.3 operationalisation	CRG	Causality-based methodology formally adopted; two-phase process (bullet points + thematic synthesis); final labour division for D3.3; treatment of evolution in causal links
WS / WP2 ↔ D3	19 May 2026	Working session	WP2 ↔ D3.3 articulation	CRG + UNITO	Triangulation logic between regional WP2 typology and local WP4 grid; agreed protocol (CRG formulates questions, UNITO answers from existing data)

Beyond the meetings listed in the table, a steering work was also done during the three physical consortium meetings (Brno, March 2025; Turin, October 2025; Lyon, March 2026), where methodological discussions could be deepened in person. It is the same for the monthly **WP3-WP4** coordination meetings hosted by AU and CRG.

2.3. Bi-Monthly Meetings intersection with WP3 tasks

The steering committee operates at the intersection of the three **WP3** tasks.

The articulation with **T3.1 (analytical grid)** has taken the form of a continuous feedback loop. The **D3.1** grid is the starting material of the bi-monthly meetings: each presenting team mobilises it, comments on it, identifies its blind spots and proposes additions. The CRG team consolidates these

feedback – in particular through Working Session #4 (March 2025) and integrates them into a progressively refined version of the toolkit. The detail of this maturation is the object of Section 3.

The articulation with **T3.3 (comparative analysis and typology)** has been more sequential.

- Until BM #5 (October 2025), the steering committee was primarily focused on the cluster presentations and the grid refinement.
- From BM #4 onwards (and explicitly from BM #6), the focus shifted toward the preparation of the comparative work: identification of cross-cluster patterns and dimensions, design of the methodological architecture for **D3.3**, allocation of thematic leadership among partners.
- BM #7 (February 2026) marks the formal transition into **T3.3** mode: it is the first meeting without a cluster presentation, fully dedicated to operationalising the comparative work. This transition is documented in Section 5.

2.4. Bi-Monthly Meetings intersection with other Work Packages

The steering committee has also been the place where the articulation between **WP3** and the other work packages. In particular **WP2 (spatial analysis and regional mapping)** has been progressively designed. Several of these articulations were already stressed in the agreement. The steering committee has also been the place where the articulation between **WP3** and the other work packages has been progressively designed, as summarised below.

Table 4 Articulation of T3.2 with other WPs

Work Package	Nature of the articulation with WP3	How it was designed / settled
WP4 – cluster case studies	Provides the empirical substance (T4.1 thematic interviews, T4.3 historical reconstruction, T4.4 actor and network mapping, T4.5 skills and competencies survey). Bi-monthly meetings shared each team’s WP4 progress and confronted the WP3 grid with the WP4 material.	Key insight (Working Session #4, March 2025): the grid must work across all WP4 tasks, not only T4.1 interviews. Some categories (actors, networks, skills, changes over time) are fed only by later tasks (T4.3 , T4.4 , T4.5) – hence certain grid categories were deliberately left partially open in the early phase of T3.2 .
WP2 – spatial analysis and regional mapping	Operates at the regional level with quantitative data (MobyGames-based geolocalised mapping, regional typology of European video game clusters, longitudinal demography). Granularity mismatch with the cluster-local WP4 case studies was a recurring concern, raised at BM #7 (Feb 2026) by the UNITO team.	Settled at the CRG–UNITO Working Session (19 May 2026) through a triangulation logic : convergences and divergences between the regional WP2 typology and the local WP4 analysis become a comparative result in themselves, rather than forcing WP2 outputs into the WP4 framework. Detailed in Section 3.7.
WP5 – Interactive toolkit	Aims to provide a practitioner-oriented translation of the project’s findings. Discussed at BMs #6 and #7, with the	Proposed solution (BM #7): a concurrent engineering approach – the bullet points

	concern that the WP5 timeline needs typology inputs before the formal D3.3 deadline.	and thematic syntheses produced for D3.3 are mobilised in real time (not after submission) to feed the WP5 toolkit.
WP6 – D3.4 recommendations	D3.4 (led by PNPTC) will deliver the operational recommendations.	Formalised in two ways: (i) the recommendations structure is co-designed by PNPTC with iterative input from the typology team, so typology dimensions feed directly into it; (ii) the same concurrent-engineering logic applies – D3.3 bullet points and syntheses already produce inputs for the recommendations, accelerating both.

3. THE ANALYTICAL TOOLKIT: MATURATION OF THE WP3 GRID

3.1. Starting Point: The consolidated D3.1 analytical grid

The starting material of the work documented in this section is the **consolidated analytical grid delivered in D3.1** (M8). The grid was designed to ensure empirical comparability across the six case studies while leaving sufficient room for cluster-specific specificities. It is organised in four main components, each subdivided into a set of categories and sub-categories:

- **Component A – Influencing factors:** contextual, economic, institutional, social, cultural and educational drivers that shape cluster emergence and development; comparative positioning with respect to other clusters in the same country, in Europe, and worldwide; relations between the cluster and its broader environment.
- **Component B – Cluster features and components:** types and roles of cluster actors (companies, institutions, training organisations, intermediaries, individual decisive actors); structural features (formal vs informal architecture, governance arrangements, leadership configurations); collaboration dimensions and the kinds of resources mobilised within the cluster.
- **Component C – Cluster dynamics:** origins and emergence (founding events, tipping points, initiating actors); evolution of the cluster over time; knowledge and resource dynamics; changes in membership and stakeholder configuration; collective activities and their evolution.
- **Component D – Impacts and performance:** benefits for the cluster members and stakeholders; disadvantages and tensions; effects on the wider territory; sustainability.

3.2. Stage 1: Conceptual Refinements shaped by the first bi-monthly meetings.

The first key stage of the **T3.2** facilitation work – **December 2024 to March 2025** – consisted in confronting the **D3.1** grid with the first two case studies (Dundee and Turin) and consolidating the feedback through a dedicated working session. Three meetings shaped this stage: **BM #1 Dundee** (17 December 2024), **BM #2 Turin** (24 February 2025), and **Working Session #4** (7 March 2025), explicitly planned at the end of BM #1 as a follow-up. By the end of this stage, **six conceptual** moves had been collectively adopted; they constitute the methodological backbone of the refined toolkit.

3.2.1. *Useful vs less useful categories: a structural reading of the divergence*

The first systematic feedback on the **D3.1** grid was delivered by the AU team at BM #1 (Dundee). The team had mobilised the grid through an inductive coding process performed in NVivo, generating 54 codes that were progressively mapped onto the grid. The feedback was structured around three observations:

- the **most useful categories** for the Dundee material were: *Social context and cultural influences, Collaboration and networks, Circulation of people, Performance of collective activities*;
- the **less useful categories** were: *Industrial structure, Strategy and leadership, Management and execution, Governance efficiency, Membership changes and performance* – all categories framed around the formal aspects of a cluster;
- the team proposed to **add** four categories to the grid: *Future of the cluster, Legacy of the cluster, Complementary services as a new category of stakeholders, Space of independent organisations and collectives*.

Two months later, at BM #2 (Turin), the UNITO team delivered convergent feedback. The categories identified as less useful overlapped almost entirely with those flagged by AU (*Strategy and leadership, Management and execution, Membership and stakeholder changes*). The most useful categories also converged, although UNITO emphasised additional ones – *Influencing factors, Cluster features and components, Cluster dynamics* – while flagging an absence: no category in the grid captured the **performance of the cluster** as such.

This convergence is analytically meaningful. Where the original interpretation could have been that the grid was simply weak on certain categories, the convergence between AU (Dundee) and UNITO (Turin) – both informal clusters – suggested a different reading: the “less useful” categories were precisely those that **presupposed formal arrangements** that did not exist in these two cases. Membership categories failed not because the grid was poorly designed, but because there was no formal membership to code. Leadership categories failed not for lack of leadership, but because leadership operated informally and was scattered across multiple individuals.

This interpretive move – from “grid weakness” to “structural reading of the divergence” – set the tone for the subsequent refinements. The question became: How can the grid be reframed so that

it captures what is going on in informal clusters, **without losing its analytical purchase on formal ones?**

3.2.2. From static to processual: adding verbs to categories

The first answer to that question was proposed by Stefano De Paoli at Working Session #4 and accepted by the facilitation team. The observation is simple but consequential. The categories of the grid in their **D3.1** form are **nouns**: *industrial structure, governance, membership, leadership*. Nouns are inherently static – they invite the identification of an object that either exists or does not exist. If the object does not exist, the category appears empty.

The proposal is to **read each category as also pointing to a process** – to add, at least conceptually, a verb to each noun. *Industrial structure* invites the identification of a fixed configuration; *structuring the industry* invites the identification of the actions through which actors progressively shape that configuration. *Governance* points to a system of decision-making; *governing* points to the practices through which decisions are actually taken, coordination is enacted, and disputes are resolved. *Leadership* points to a position; *leading* points to the practices through which orientation is given to a collective effort. This processual reframing has two operational consequences:

- First, it makes the grid usable on informal clusters, in which the relevant phenomena exist as processes rather than as objects: Dundee has no formal cluster governance, but it has a continuous activity of *governing* – coordinated by AU University, by informal gatherings, by individual industry veterans, by the meetups and the pub conversations identified in the codebook.
- Second, it pushes the grid in a direction that proved consistent with the subsequent methodological choices of the project (Section 3.6): a focus on **mechanisms** rather than on configurations.

The two readings are not mutually exclusive. The grid retains its categorial structure for the description of static features (which are useful for some clusters), and it adds a processual reading for the description of dynamic features (which are essential for others). The trade-off was made explicit at WS #4: certain categories will be filled in a static mode for one cluster and in a processual mode for another, and this difference of mode is itself an analytical result.

3.2.3. Organisation vs organising: a conceptual import from organisation studies

A more theoretical refinement was proposed at WS #4, drawing on the academic work of **Silvia Gherardi** (Gherardi, 2006; Gherardi and Strati, 2012). The distinction is between **organisation** – the system, the structure, the formal architecture of an arrangement – and **organising** – the coordinating activity through which a collective effort is enacted as a process. A parallel reference to **Erhard Friedberg and Michel Crozier** (Crozier and Friedberg, 1977), whose distinction between formal and informal organisation occupies a similar conceptual terrain in French sociology of organisations was made during the same session.

The relevance for **GAME-ER** is direct. Some of the project's clusters have an *organisation* in the strong sense (Lyon's Game-Only, Bordeaux's SoGames, Brno's Game_Cluster); others have **no organisation but a substantial activity of organising** (Dundee, partly Turin). When the grid asks about "governance" or "membership", it implicitly addresses the organisation level; if it is to capture the organising level as well, it needs to be read with this distinction in mind.

The conceptual move has two downstream consequences within the project:

- it provides a **vocabulary** for naming what happens in informal clusters without forcing them into a language designed for formal ones;
- it allows the grid to **discriminate between clusters along a continuum** of organisation/organising rather than along a binary formal/informal opposition; Brno, for instance, can be read as a cluster in active transition from organising to organisation, with all the tensions that such a transition involves (the Game_Cluster's debate on membership fees, the disagreements over the lobbying role following the 2024 audiovisual law);

3.2.4. The three irreducible methodological tensions

The third move was also proposed at WS #4. Its function is less to refine the grid than to **make explicit the structure of the methodological choices that must be made when applying it**. The proposition is that the analytical work on a cluster is structured by three irreducible tensions:

- **the cluster as ecosystem vs the cluster as association** – i.e. the difference between studying the wide field of actors, relations and activities present on a territory, and studying a specific institutional construct (the formal cluster organisation, when it exists);
- **the holistic viewpoint vs the companies' viewpoint** – i.e. the difference between treating the cluster as a unit of analysis in itself, and treating it from the point of view of the individual firms that inhabit it, with their strategies, resources and motivations;
- **the static analysis vs the longitudinal analysis** – i.e. the difference between describing the cluster at a given point in time, and tracing its evolution over time, with attention to phases, tipping points and trajectories.

These three tensions are irreducible in the sense that no single research strategy can fully address all three at once. Trying to do so produces a complexity that is "quite impossible to grasp". The implication is operational: for each category of the grid, the analyst must **make explicit which side of each tension is being addressed**. Some categories are best treated holistically, others firm-by-firm; some statically, others longitudinally; some at the ecosystem level, others at the association level. This proposition does not solve the tensions, but it formalises them. This **disciplines the comparative work**, by ensuring that all teams treat each category in a consistent mode and it **opens a space for explicit methodological choices**, where the trade-offs become themselves the object of reflection – a posture that is consistent with the causality-based methodology eventually adopted at BM #7 (Section 3.6).

3.2.5. Dismantling “membership”: territorial presence, collaboration involvement, sense of belonging

The fourth move concerns the single most contested category of the original grid: **membership**. The category had been flagged as less useful by both AU and UNITO. The reasons converged across cases: in Dundee, there is no formal cluster organisation, so membership in the institutional sense has no referent; in Turin, the cluster is informal and many local actors resist the very idea of formalised membership; in Brno, membership is individual rather than corporate, which generates a series of governance ambiguities discussed at length in BM #3. The category had also generated confusions in the French clusters, where Lyon’s Game-Only and Bordeaux’s SoGames have well-defined formal memberships, but where the broader ecosystem extends well beyond the membership boundary.

At WS #4, the consensus emerged that “membership” as a single category does too much work, and that it should be **decomposed**. Three more workable concepts were extracted from the discussion:

- **Territorial presence** – is the firm physically located on the territory of the cluster? This is the most basic question, and it is operationally tractable for all six cases.
- **Collaboration involvement** – is the firm engaged in collaborative activities (project work, mutual support, knowledge exchange, joint lobbying, shared events) with other firms on the territory, and what are the nature and the frequency of these collaborations?
- **Sense of belonging** – does the firm recognise itself as part of the cluster, and what does this recognition entail in terms of identity, posture, and behaviour?

The decomposition has a strong analytical payoff. It allows the cases that resisted the “membership” category (Dundee, Turin) to be addressed through the three sub-questions, each of which is independently tractable. It allows the cases with formal membership (Lyon, Bordeaux, Brno) to be analysed both at the level of formal membership and at the level of the broader ecosystem.<<for instance, identifying which firms on the territory are not formal members of Game-Only but are nonetheless involved in collaborations, or, conversely, which formal members are largely inactive in the collaboration tissue. It also allows the cases like Turin’s, where **the sense of belonging is strong but no formal mechanism enacts it**, to be properly described and, conversely, the cases like one historical Lyon studio’s, where collaboration was extensive but sense of belonging was explicitly denied by the founder, can also be coded with precision.

Thomas Paris expressed reservations about the term *sense of belonging* on the grounds of its subjective character. The reservation is taken up in Section 5 as a methodological caveat. The trade-off accepted at WS#4 is that subjectivity, when consistently codified across cases, is itself an analytical resource, particularly in case studies based on interview material, where actors’ self-positioning is part of the data.

3.2.6. Integrating proximity grids

The sixth move integrates a conceptual resource imported from economic geography: **Ron Boschma’s grid of proximities**. Boschma’s framework (Boschma, 2005) which identifies five forms of proximity (cognitive, organisational, social, institutional, geographical) – provides a fine-grained vocabulary for describing the kinds of relations that hold a cluster together. The proposition formulated during the WS #4 discussion was to integrate these five forms of proximity as **sub-categories** within the *Collaboration features* component of the grid.

The integration has two operational consequences. First, it refines the analytical resolution of the grid on what is arguably its most central question: the nature of the ties between cluster actors. Rather than treating “collaboration” as a single dimension, the grid can now distinguish between cognitive proximity (shared knowledge bases, technical conventions, professional vocabularies), organisational proximity (shared formal arrangements, common institutional belongings), social proximity (interpersonal ties, friendships, shared career histories), institutional proximity (shared regulatory and normative environments) and geographical proximity (physical co-location and its consequences). Second, it provides a **bridge to the existing cluster literature**, allowing the **GAME-ER** findings to be positioned in dialogue with a well-established conceptual tradition. This bridge will be exploited in **D3.3** and in the academic publications derived from the project.

The integration of Boschma’s grid was operationally tested in two case studies during Key Stage 2 (Section 3.3): the Lyon analysis (BM #5) explicitly mobilised the distinction between cognitive, social and institutional proximity to describe the legacy of Infogrames; the Turin analysis (BM #2) implicitly mobilised cognitive and social proximity to describe the close-knit community of the four founding studios. The convention adopted is that the five proximities are used as sub-categories in the *Collaboration features* component, while remaining usable as an independent analytical lens when the case calls for it.

3.3. Stage 2: Codebook construction across teams

Key Stage 2 of the facilitation work – **April 2025 to November 2025** – consisted in the systematic application of the refined grid to the four remaining case studies: Brno (BM #3), Fundão (BM #4), Lyon (BM #5), and Bordeaux (BM #6). Each team produced a codebook adapted to its case, and the bi-monthly meetings became the venue where these codebooks were shared, compared and discussed.

The codebooks that emerged are heterogeneous in their structure, their granularity, and their tooling. This heterogeneity is itself an analytical resource: it reflects the diversity of disciplinary backgrounds, methodological preferences and case-specific challenges across the teams. The role of **T3.2** was not to impose codebook uniformity (which would have flattened these productive differences), but to ensure that all codebooks could be **mapped back onto the WP3 grid**, so that the comparative work of **D3.3** has a consistent reading layer.

3.3.1. Shared template structure

The shared template structure that emerged across teams – converging on the format first shared by CRG team then adopted and refined by AU at BM #1 and adopted (with adaptations) by UNITO, CUNI, INOVA+ and CRG articulates four hierarchical levels:

- **Themes** (or large codes) – the top level, typically corresponding to a major component of the cluster (the cluster itself, the city, the company / worker level, the national industry). Themes are stable across the codebook and serve as the principal organising axis. They typically number between 4 and 6.
- **Codes** – the operational level, each capturing a substantive aspect of the cluster (e.g. *associations, informal relations, educational institutions, audiovisual law lobbying*). The number of codes varies between 18 (INOVA+ for Fundão) and 54 (AU for Dundee), reflecting the differences in case complexity and coding strategy.
- **Sub-codes** – the granular level, each capturing a specific dimension of a code (e.g. under *informal relations*: lunches, dinners, IGDA gatherings, Tech in Tonic events). The number of sub-codes varies markedly across cases – from a few dozen to over eighty for Turin.
- **Sub-sub-codes** (for some teams) – the case-specific level, capturing very specific items such as a single institution or a single event. UNITO uses this level systematically; other teams use it more sparingly.

In addition, each codebook carries a column of **definitions**, which has proven essential in the cross-cluster discussions. As repeatedly observed during the bi-monthly meetings (especially WS #4 and BM #3), the same word may carry significantly different meanings across cases – *governance* in Lyon is not *governance* in Dundee – and the definitions column makes these semantic differences explicit and tractable.

3.3.2. Tools mobilised across teams

Three coding tools have been used by the consortium teams, sometimes in combination:

- **NVivo** – the most widely used qualitative coding software has been the primary tool for the AU (Dundee), UNITO (Turin), and CUNI (Brno) teams. AU performed the initial coding manually with NVivo support, then ran an iterative process of code refinement; the team reported at BM #1 that “a stable version emerged and was mapped into the analytical grid”. UNITO produced two successive versions of the codebook in NVivo (the first in Italian, the second translated into English while keeping interview extracts in Italian); a third version was planned. CUNI followed a comparable trajectory.
- **ChatGPT-assisted coding** has been experimented by two teams. The INOVA+ team (Fundão) reported at BM #4 a substantial deployment of ChatGPT to support the inductive coding of 28 interviews, using prompts initially shared by Stefano De Paoli (who had developed a similar prompt application for AU). The team identified three operational pitfalls:

- (i) tendency of the model to **summarise responses excessively**, producing too short a list of codes; mitigated by explicitly requesting a minimum number of codes per interview;
- (ii) (ii) **data volume limitation** preventing the upload of the full corpus at once; mitigated by processing each interview individually;
- (iii) the production of **fake quotes** when the model was asked to illustrate codes with examples from the corpus; mitigated by explicitly prompting the model not to fabricate quotes.

The team also stressed that the deployment was made possible by a privacy-respecting institutional account that does not feed user data into the training pipeline. The conclusion drawn at BM #4 by Tânia Moreira was that “the human coding still remains the best, but ChatGPT is quite helpful in digesting all this information; it does not work alone – we always need to check what it is doing.”

A complementary experimentation, mentioned at BM #1 by AU, has run a **dual-approach coding** in parallel: manual NVivo coding alongside AI-assisted coding, with the two approaches reportedly converging. This kind of cross-validation, when systematised, may become a methodological contribution worth documenting in its own right.

Manual coding without dedicated software has remained the practice of the CRG team for the Lyon and Bordeaux cases, in tandem with extensive documentary analysis (around 130 documents for Lyon).

3.3.3. Multilingual coding and the question of translation

The six case studies span five languages: English (Dundee), Italian (Turin), Czech (Brno), Portuguese (Fundão), and French (Lyon, Bordeaux). The implications for the coding work are significant and have been discussed repeatedly during the bi-monthly meetings – notably at BM #2 (Turin), where UNITO emphasised that “there are semiotic peculiarities that cannot be translated and reproduced in English”, and at BM #4 (Fundão), where INOVA+ described the trade-offs of a complete translation pipeline. Three conventions have been adopted across the consortium:

- **Codes and sub-codes are systematically translated into English** in the final codebook version of each team, to ensure cross-cluster comparability. The translation is done by the team itself, often in iterative passes (UNITO produced one Italian version then an English version with extracts kept in Italian).
- **Interview extracts may remain in the original language** in the team’s internal coding files but are translated when used for cross-cluster discussion or in the WP4 deliverables.
- **Semantic specificities** that resist translation are flagged in the definition column of the codebook and discussed during the bi-monthly meetings when they bear on comparative analysis.

The trade-offs are not symmetric across cases. The Portuguese-to-English translation for Fundão has been done at scale, with the team taking the position that “the raw data in English is useful for future research” (BM #4). The Italian-to-English translation for Turin has been more conservative,

with the team prioritising semantic fidelity over coverage. The French cases (Lyon, Bordeaux) have been coded directly in French, with translation reserved for the cross-cluster comparison and for the deliverables. These different choices are documented and respected; they do not impair the comparative work as long as the codebook structure remains mappable onto the WP3 grid.

3.3.4. Inductive vs deductive coding, and the abductive compromise

A recurring methodological discussion across the bi-monthly meetings has concerned the **balance between inductive and deductive coding**. Pure inductive coding lets the codes emerge from the data, without prior commitment to the grid; pure deductive coding applies the grid directly as a coding scheme, with the risk of forcing the data into pre-defined categories. Each team has had to navigate this trade-off.

The dominant approach across the consortium has been abductive – a mixed inductive-deductive process in which the initial coding is performed inductively, then the codes are mapped onto the grid, with iterative refinement of both the codes and (where relevant) the grid itself. UNITO described its approach at BM #2 as a “semi-inductive process informed by the analytical grid, where the overlap is not perfect at this moment, but the results are quite good”. CUNI followed a comparable strategy at BM #3. AU’s dual-approach (manual NVivo + AI) reinforces the abductive logic by running two coding processes in parallel and using their convergences as a validation device.

A specific experiment was conducted by INOVA+ during the Fundação coding (BM #4) and discussed in detail by Chahira Mehouchi: **explicitly using ChatGPT in inductive then deductive mode** on the same corpus, to compare the codes that emerge inductively with those that the grid would predict deductively. The two-mode comparison was presented at BM #4 as a work in progress; its preliminary outputs suggest that the inductive codes broadly overlap with the grid but introduce sub-categories that the grid does not anticipate (notably around **public recognition** and **socio-cultural barriers**).

The abductive compromise has shaped the operational use of the grid. Rather than treating the grid as a fixed coding scheme to be applied uniformly, the teams treat it as a **reference architecture** against which their own codebooks are mapped, with explicit identification of where the team’s codes align with the grid, where they extend it, and where they diverge from it. This mapping is itself the principal methodological output of **T3.2** for the comparative work of **D3.3**, and it is documented in **Annex E** (synoptic table: codebooks vs WP3 grid, per cluster).

3.4. Cluster Narrative Reconstruction

The second major analytical practice that consolidated during Key Stage 2 is the **narrative reconstruction of each cluster’s history**. This practice was introduced at BM #1 with the AU team, in the form of a tentative timeline of the Dundee cluster reconstructed from the interview corpus and the documentary work. The proposition that emerged from the discussion was the formalisation of the “timeline as the primary analytical tool” for understanding cluster emergence and evolution.

The timeline practice has subsequently been adopted by all the presenting teams, with progressive refinement of its structure and analytical depth. By BM #5 (Lyon, October 2025), it had matured into a fully articulated framework, which now serves as a candidate template for the cross-cluster comparative work in **D3.3**.

3.4.1. The timeline as primary analytical tool

The function of the timeline is not chronological but **analytical**. It serves three purposes:

- **identify the major phases** of the cluster’s trajectory, each defined by a distinctive configuration of actors, activities and orientations;
- **locate the tipping points** between phases (the events, crises or decisions that have triggered structural reconfigurations);
- **identify the catalysts** of cluster development across phases – the recurring mechanisms (crises, public support, anchor firm legacy, generational handovers) that have driven the cluster’s evolution.

The timeline is therefore the place where the **static description of the cluster’s features** (Component B of the grid) meets the **dynamic analysis of its evolution** (Component C). It is also the place where the **causal links** between contextual factors, actor decisions and structural outcomes become most visible – which is why the timeline practice prefigured the causality-based methodology subsequently adopted for **D3.3**.

The case studies have produced timelines of varying granularity. Turin’s timeline (BM #2) traced the cluster from 2000 (Virtuality Conference) through 2014 (“year zero”) to 2020 (first IGDA Italy chapter) and beyond, identifying a smaller number of phases consistent with the cluster’s youth. Brno’s timeline (BM #3) emphasised the institutional formation of the Game Cluster as a turning point and the 2024 audiovisual law as a transformative episode. Fundão’s timeline (BM #4) was structured around three macro-phases (proto-cluster, 2010s–early 2020s, recent specialisation phase) and emphasised the 2012 Innovation Plan as the foundational policy event. Bordeaux’s timeline (BM #6) was presented with a strategic focus on the 2002–2007 transition period between the Callisto collapse and the creation of SoGames, on the analytical hypothesis that **the recreation of an industrial cluster from a near-empty starting point is the most revealing moment of cluster dynamics**.

Lyon analysis (BM #5) articulated a **six-phase model** of the cluster’s trajectory: foundation with Infogrames (1983–1996), crisis and spin-off wave (1997 onwards), Lyon Game (2002–2005), Imaginove and the institutionalisation leap (2005–2019), the late-Imaginove decline, and the Game-Only renaissance (2019 onwards). The model is one of the most analytically dense outputs of Key Stage 2, and it is one of the candidate templates for the comparative narrative work in **D3.3**.

3.4.2. Articulation with the historical analysis task (T4.3)

The narrative reconstruction work conducted during the bi-monthly meetings is preliminary in nature as it draws on the **T4.1** interview material and on the documentary, work done by each team, but it precedes the formal historical task **T4.3**, which is dedicated to the in-depth media-

historiographical reconstruction of each cluster’s emergence. The articulation has been managed pragmatically: the bi-monthly timelines provide a working draft, which is then enriched and revised by the **T4.3** historical work as it progresses.

At BM #2 (Turin), this articulation was made explicit. The UNITO team presented their timeline as “derived mostly from first-hand accounts gathered in the previous task and from things we just know about the situation”, with the understanding that **T4.3** was still at an early stage. The same pattern was observed at BM #6 (Bordeaux), where the presentation focused on the 2002–2007 transition as a deliberately selected analytical entry point, knowing that the full historical reconstruction was being conducted in parallel.

3.4.3. Reference to Langley’s temporal bracketing

A complementary methodological reference was introduced at WS #4 by Chahira Mehouachi: **Ann Langley’s temporal bracketing strategy**, a recognised approach in qualitative process research. Temporal bracketing consists in decomposing a process into a sequence of phases, each treated as an independent unit of analysis with its own structural features, then analysing the transitions between phases as the operative analytical material.

The relevance for **GAME-ER** is twofold. First, it provides a **methodological warrant** for the timeline practice: temporal bracketing is a documented and tested approach for combining static and longitudinal analysis on the same case, addressing precisely the “static vs longitudinal” tension formalised in Section 3.2.4. Second, it provides a **conceptual tool** for the causal analysis to come: by treating each phase as an internally coherent configuration and the transitions as the moments where causal mechanisms become visible, temporal bracketing aligns naturally with the causality-based methodology adopted for **D3.3**. The reference will be developed more substantially in **D3.3**, where temporal bracketing is one of the candidate methods for treating the **evolution of causal links over time** a question raised by the facilitation team at BM #7.

3.5. New categories added to the grid

The two stages documented so far have produced a refined version of the WP3 grid in two distinct ways: through **conceptual moves** that reframe how the existing categories should be read (Section 3.2), and through **codebook practice** that maps each team’s substantive coding onto the grid (Section 3.3). A third pathway has operated alongside these two: the **progressive addition of new categories** that the bi-monthly meetings revealed to be analytically necessary but absent from the original grid.

Six additions deserve to be documented here, because they will be carried into the comparative work of **D3.3** and into the eventual update of the grid itself.

Table 5 Added categories to the analytical grid

Added category	Captures
Future of the cluster	Prospective discourse of actors (what they expect, what they fear, what they consider as plausible trajectories). It proved consequential in nearly all subsequent cases, notably in Brno (the debate over the “end of the golden era” of the Game_Cluster) and in Lyon (the cluster’s strategy of autonomy from public funding)
Legacy of the cluster	Long-term structuring effect of past configurations (e.g. Infogrames in Lyon, Callisto in Bordeaux, DMA in Dundee) on the present functioning of the cluster. It proved central in Dundee (the DMA Design legacy and the cluster’s reputation built on it), in Lyon (the Infogrames legacy structuring the cluster’s DNA for 25 years), and in Bordeaux (the Callisto collapse leaving a tissue of alumni networks and IPs that reincubated the cluster). But less in other clusters.
Complementary services	Service providers to the cluster (training, legal, technical, mentoring) that are not game developers
Independent organisations and collectives	It refers to the informal organisations, employee-driven initiatives and counter-cultural spaces that exist alongside the main formal arrangements, and whose role in the cluster’s identity and functioning is often disproportionate to their formal weight.
Entry mechanisms	How new firms / actors enter the core network (insider / outsider dynamics). In Turin, a “second wave” of firms emerged around 2022 through the QuickLoad accelerator, and a wider network of small firms and solo developers exists outside the main core; the question of how these peripheral actors do or do not enter the central network became analytically important.
Sense of belonging	Symbolic and identity dimension of the actor’s relation to the cluster, distinct from membership and collaboration. It proved necessary to describe cases such as Turin (where the sense of belonging is strong despite the resistance to formalisation). The subjective character of this category requires careful operational handling. The convention adopted is that the category is coded based on actor-level discourse data (how interviewees position themselves in relation to the cluster) rather than on inferred or imputed belonging.
Informal coordination (transversal reframing)	Systematic doubling of formal categories that were originally framed in formal terms (governance, leadership, strategy) to capture their informal enactment

Note: The grid refinements documented here are operational adjustments rather than a formal revision of **D3.1**. They constitute the working version of the grid used for **D3.3**.

3.6. The causality-based methodological turn

The work documented in Sections 3.2 to 3.5 has progressively refined the analytical grid into an operational toolkit. But the move from refined toolkit to actual comparative analysis required an additional methodological decision:

What kind of comparison is to be performed across the six cases, and what kind of typology is to be produced?

This question was the object of a deliberate decision-making sequence that culminated at BM #7 (24 February 2026): the adoption of a **causality-based methodology**. The decision is consequential enough to warrant detailed documentation. This sub-section presents its rationale (3.6.1), its epistemological status (3.6.2), and its treatment of evolution over time (3.6.3).

3.6.1. Why a causality-based approach: the sample size argument

The argument was formulated at BM #7. With **six clusters in the comparative panel** – Dundee, Turin, Brno, Fundão, Lyon, Bordeaux – the **GAME-ER** project does not have, and cannot pretend to have, a sample large enough to support a statistically grounded typology. Any attempt to derive cluster types through frequency-based or statistical methods would over-interpret the available cases and would be vulnerable to criticism on representativeness grounds.

What six well-documented case studies *can* support, however, is the **identification of micro-mechanisms and configurational causalities** – the chains of events, decisions and consequences that link contextual factors to cluster outcomes, and that can be traced with confidence within each case and compared across cases. This shift of analytical target – from frequencies to mechanisms – is the central move of the methodology adopted for **D3.3**.

The implication is operational. Each team will be asked to identify, within its case material, **the causal links between observable features of the cluster** (its actors, its institutional arrangements, its economic conditions) **and the dynamics that the cluster has displayed over time** (its emergence, its phases, its tensions, its current configuration). These causal links – formulated as configurational propositions of the form “given context X and actor configuration Y, mechanism Z produced outcome W” – become the analytical primitives of the comparative work. The typology is then built **from the convergences and divergences in these causal configurations across cases**, rather than from statistical regularities in cluster attributes.

About the specific methodological approach and how to apply it operationally, there were several discussions about the relevance of the QCA – the **Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) tradition** developed by Charles Ragin (Ragin, 1987; Ragin, 2008) and his successors (Rihoux et Ragin, 2009; Schneider et Wagemann, 2012). QCA is a methodology designed precisely for comparative situations where there is a moderate number of cases (typically 5 to 50), each documented in qualitative depth, and a research question oriented toward the identification of **causal configurations** rather than statistical regularities. The convention adopted for **GAME-ER** is that QCA is mobilised as a methodological *reference* and an *analytical lens*, rather than as a strict procedural framework: the comparative work will draw on QCA’s emphasis on configurational causality and on

the analysis of necessary and sufficient conditions, without committing to the formal Boolean minimisation procedures that characterise the canonical QCA toolkit.

3.6.2. Epistemological status of causality with qualitative data

The methodological choice raises a classical epistemological question, which was discussed at BM #7: qualitative data – and in particular interview-based qualitative data – does not lend itself easily to strong causal claims in the positivist sense.

The position adopted by the consortium, and articulated during BM #7, can be summarised in three propositions.

- First, the kind of causality at stake is **not causality in the positivist sense**. As Stefano De Paoli put it, “it is not causality in the positivistic sense of the term: if people say they did this because of something else, that is what they are suggesting. This is fine with qualitative data, as long as we don’t make generalised claims that this is the objective reality of things.” The causal claims of the typology are claims about **mechanisms that actors themselves identify** in their accounts of cluster dynamics, not claims about objective causal regularities independent of actor interpretation.
- Second, the methodological anchorage is in **methodological individualism and research-action traditions** – a position articulated during BM #7 with reference to the sociological tradition of organisational analysis (Crozier and Friedberg, 1977) and to the broader interpretive turn in social science methodology. In this tradition, causality is reconstructed from the meaning that actors give to their actions, and from the regularities that emerge in the accounts of multiple actors confronted with comparable situations.
- Third, the analytical power of this approach is **comparative**: a causal mechanism identified in one case study acquires its force when it is found again – in identical or modified form – in another case study. The typology is therefore built on **patterns of causal recurrence across cases**, not on the certainty of any single causal claim within a case.

This epistemological position is consistent with the case study tradition in management research and economic sociology, and it is operationally compatible with the kind of comparative material produced through the bi-monthly meetings: actor-level discourse from interviews, complemented by documentary analysis and contextualised by the historical work of **T4.3**.

3.6.3. Handling the evolution of causal links over time

A specific methodological challenge raised by the causality-based approach concerns the **evolution of causal mechanisms over time**. The point was raised at BM #7 and is consequential enough to deserve its own treatment.

The empirical situation is the following: the case studies span very different temporal depths. The Lyon cluster has a 40-year history (1983 onwards); the Bordeaux cluster a comparable depth; Turin is younger (the “year zero” being 2013–2014); Fundão is in its proto-cluster phase (the Innovation Plan dating from 2012). For the older clusters, **the same causal link does not necessarily operate in the same way across the cluster’s history**. In Lyon, for instance, the causal link between *institutional*

context and *collective action* – mediated by the *availability of public resources* – has gone through at least three distinct configurations across the six phases of the cluster’s evolution: the Lyon Game phase, the Imaginove phase, and the Game-Only phase.

Two methodological options are available:

- **Snapshot approach** – focus the causal analysis on the current state of the cluster, treating older phases as background. This approach simplifies the comparative work but loses analytical depth on the older clusters, and it is not consistent with the grant agreement’s emphasis on cluster history.
- **Phase-bracketed approach** – identify the major phases of the cluster’s history and analyse the causal mechanisms operating in each phase, then trace the **transformations of the causal links across phases**.

The consortium has retained the phase-bracketed approach, with explicit reference to Langley’s temporal bracketing strategy (Section 3.4.3). Operationally, this means that the bullet points produced by each team during Phase 1 of D3.3 (Section 5.4.) will include, for each major causal link identified, a **report of how that causal link has evolved across the phases of the cluster’s history**. The convention adopted is that the team reports the **major phases** of the causal link and the **triggers** of the transformations between phases, rather than tracking every micro-change.

This phase-bracketed treatment has the additional benefit of feeding directly into the **resilience and meta-organisational capacity** question raised at BM #5 in the discussion of the Lyon case. The capacity of a cluster to dissolve and reconstruct its formal organisation while preserving the underlying organising activity – observed paradigmatically in the Lyon trajectory (From Lyon Game - to Imaginove - to Game-Only) – is precisely the kind of phenomenon that a phase-bracketed causal analysis is designed to capture. It is therefore one of the candidate dimensions of the comparative work in D3.3.

Summary: the methodological architecture

By the end of Key Stage 3 (Section 5), the methodological architecture for D3.3 had crystallised into the following set of choices:

- **Comparative target** – micro-mechanisms and configurational causalities, not statistical regularities;
- **Epistemological status** – causality as actor-level reconstruction of cluster dynamics, not as positivist causal regularity;
- **Temporal treatment** – phase-bracketed, with explicit reporting of the evolution of causal links across phases;
- **Analytical grid** – the WP3 grid as refined through Sections 3.2–3.5, with explicit attention to the static/processual distinction and to the organisation/organising distinction.

These choices are the **direct methodological output of T3.2**, and they constitute the operational basis on which the comparative work of **D3.3** is being conducted.

3.7. The articulation with WP2: triangulation rather than convergence

A final analytical question shaped Key Stage 3 of the facilitation work: **how should the WP2 outputs – produced at the regional level – be integrated with the WP4 case studies – produced at the cluster level – in the comparative work of D3.3.** The question was raised explicitly at BM #7, and it was the object of a dedicated working session held on 19 May 2026 between the CRG team and the WP2 lead (UNITO).

The articulation that emerged from this session is documented here because it is one of the conditions under which **D3.3** can deliver a typology that is empirically grounded across all the project’s WPs, and because it sets a precedent for how multi-WP integration can be handled in projects of comparable scope.

3.7.1. *The mismatch identified at BM #7*

The problem, as formulated at BM #7, is the following. WP2 has produced (through **D2.2** and **D2.3**) a set of outputs at the **regional level**, based on geolocalised data from the MobyGames database. These outputs include:

- a **company-type classification** (developer, integrated, publisher, complementary, diversified);
- a **regional typology of European video game clusters** (with categories such as *creative hotspot*, *peripheral scene*, *regional cluster*);
- **longitudinal demography** of regional clusters across five time periods (pre-1999, 2000–2004, 2005–2009, 2010–2014, 2015–2019, 2020 onwards);
- **geolocalised maps** that can be produced at the city level as well as at the regional level.

The case study work of **WP4**, by contrast, has produced material at the **cluster level** – typically the city or the metropolitan area – based on interview data, documentary analysis, and qualitative coding. The two levels of granularity do not overlap directly. The spatial analysis has been carried out at the regional level, not at the cluster level necessarily.

The mismatch follows directly from the **WP2** design, which was intentionally regional-scale to provide European-wide comparability. But it requires an explicit articulation strategy for **D3.3**.

3.7.2. *The triangulation principle*

The articulation principle adopted at the 19 May 2026 working session is **triangulation rather than convergence**.

The reasoning is the following. Attempting to force the **WP2** regional outputs into the **WP4** cluster framework – or, conversely, attempting to fit the **WP4** cluster outputs into the **WP2** regional categories – would systematically lose information from one of the two sources. The two approaches capture **different objects at different scales**, and each capture what the other does not. The methodological response is therefore to **treat the convergences and divergences between the two analyses as themselves an analytical result**, rather than as a problem to be resolved.

A paradigmatic example illustrates the principle. In the **WP2** regional typology, both **Turin and Fundão are classified as “peripheral scenes”** – a category that captures comparable positions in the European spatial distribution of the industry. In the **WP4** cluster analyses, however, **Turin and Fundão are markedly different**: Turin is an older, bottom-up, community-driven cluster with substantial internal informal coordination; Fundão is a younger, top-down, policy-driven proto-cluster in active formation. The fact that the two analyses produce convergent classifications at one scale and divergent characterisations at another is itself a substantive finding: it tells the comparative work what the regional positioning of the cluster does and does not determine, and it identifies the local-level mechanisms that are operative regardless of regional positioning.

The principle was articulated by Enrico Bertacchini at the working session: “let us try to understand how we can learn from each other, from the qualitative and the quantitative approach... [rather than] try to put inside something that is not perfectly compatible.” The adoption of this principle is one of the methodological achievements of **T3.2** and provides the operational basis for the WP2 integration into **D3.3**.

3.7.3. The agreed protocol

The protocol that emerged from the 19 May 2026 session is procedurally simple and operationally tractable:

- the **CRG team formulates a list of comparative questions** of interest for **D3.3**, framed in ways that the **WP2** data can plausibly address (e.g. comparative demography of clusters, longitudinal evolution of cluster size, regional positioning of each cluster);
- the **WP2 team answers these questions from the existing data**, without launching new analyses or new data collection – the protocol is one of *reuse*, not of *new production*;
- for each question, the comparative work **identifies the convergences and divergences** between the **WP2** outputs and the **WP4** outputs, and treats these convergences and divergences as themselves analytical material;
- the resulting comparative observations are integrated into **D3.3** as a **dedicated section**, so that the **WP2** contribution to the typology is visible and properly credited.

Two priority questions were retained at the session as the first batch for the protocol: (i) comparative demography of clusters – the distribution of company sizes and types across the six cases – and (ii) longitudinal evolution of cluster growth patterns, with explicit caveat on the data fragility for the most recent periods. A third candidate – comparative typology of company types per cluster (developers, integrated, publishers) – was identified as easily tractable from the existing WP2 data and is being added to the list.

3.7.4. What WP2 can and cannot contribute to D3.3

For clarity, the following table synthesises the scope of the **WP2** contribution to **D3.3**.

Table 6 Scope of WP2 and contribution to D3.3

WP2 output	Contribution to D3.3	Caveat
Geolocalised maps (region and city)	Available, supports visual comparative analysis	City-level granularity is statistically less representative than regional
Regional typology of European clusters	Direct input to the typology dimension of D3.3	Categories built at regional scale, not cluster scale
Company-type classification per cluster	Available for each of the six cases (developer / integrated / publisher / complementary / diversified)	Based on MobyGames frequency metrics, not on direct firm survey
Longitudinal demography (5 periods)	Available, supports cross-cluster comparison of growth patterns	Fragile on the most recent period (data lag in MobyGames); requires interpretive caution
Skills and competencies data	Not available in WP2	The skills dimension of D3.3 must be sourced from T4.5 only

The skills dimension is the only **D3.3** dimension that cannot be cross validated with **WP2** data; for this dimension, the comparative work of **D3.3** will rely exclusively on the **T4.5** survey outputs (delivered by end of May 2026 at the earliest, per the BM #7 discussion).

3.7.5. Methodological status of the triangulation principle

The triangulation principle adopted for the **WP2-WP4** articulation is consistent with the broader methodological architecture documented in Sections 3.2 to 3.6. It is a specific application of the same logic: when two analytical approaches produce different readings of the same object, the analytical task is not to choose one over the other or to force their convergence, but to **make the divergence itself the object of analysis**. The same logic underpins the static/processual distinction (Section 3.2.2), the organisation/organising distinction (Section 3.2.3), the dismantling of “membership” (Section 3.2.5), and the causality-based methodology (Section 3.6).

This convergence of methodological principles across the different layers of **T3.2** is not coincidental: it reflects a consistent epistemic posture according to which **the analytical value of comparative work lies in the articulation of differences**, not in their resolution into a single dominant reading. This posture will be carried into **D3.3**, both in the comparative work itself and in the typology that emerges from it.

4. CROSS-CUTTING OUTPUTS FROM THE SEVEN BI-MONTHLY MEETINGS

The seven bi-monthly meetings and the two methodological working sessions have produced a substantial body of cross-cutting observations across the six case studies. These observations are documented in the present section. They are presented at the descriptive level – the **analytical**

synthesis of these patterns into a typology is the object of **D3.3** and is deliberately not undertaken here.

The section is organised in two sub-sections. Section 4.1 identifies the **five convergent patterns** that emerged across all or most of the cases. Section 4.2 identifies the **four discriminating dimensions** along which the cases differ in analytically meaningful ways.

These observations are the cumulative output of the steering committee’s work. They are not the result of a formal cross-cluster analysis performed by the CRG team; they are the recurring themes that have emerged in the discussions across the seven meetings, formulated in cumulative terms by participants from all the case study teams. They are therefore **observations to be tested and qualified by D3.3**, not preliminary results to be confirmed.

4.1. Five convergent patterns across the cases

Five patterns have recurred in the discussions across multiple case studies, with sufficient consistency to be considered candidates for the comparative work of **D3.3**.

4.1.1. Centrality of informal networks

Across **Dundee, Turin, Brno and Fundão**, and even within the formalised French cases (**Lyon and Bordeaux**), the informal networks of personal relations among cluster actors emerged as a central operating mechanism of the cluster. In Dundee, the cluster operates without a formal cluster organisation, and the informal connections among AU alumni, industry veterans and local meetups are the principal coordination mechanism. In Turin, the four founding studios know each other personally; the informal events (lunches, dinners, T-Union meetings) carry most of the coordination weight; even when an institutionalised event such as Tech in Tonic exists, it is described as a continuation of informal practice. In Brno, the Game_Cluster itself is institutionally informal – based on individual membership without fees, with a published *Ethical Code* that explicitly values informality and physical presence. In Fundão, the proto-cluster phase has been carried out by an “informal enthusiast-driven community” of meetups, hackathons and gatherings.

The pattern is not specific to small or young clusters. In Lyon, even within the formalised setting of Game Only, the informal coordination is described as essential: the volunteer work of mentors in the *Let’s Go* programme, the afterworks of *Lyon Game Dev*, the informal *Slack* exchanges among studio managers. In Bordeaux, the 2002–2007 transition phase was driven by the informal relations between former Callisto employees who became founders of new ventures – the formal SoGames association in 2007 being a later codification of an already-active informal network.

The cross-cluster convergence on this pattern is consistent with the broader literature on creative clusters and on industrial districts, but it acquires here a specific texture that will need to be analysed in **D3.3**: **the role of informal networks as durable coordination infrastructure, even where formal organisations are present and active.**

4.1.2. The role of tertiary education and dedicated training institutions

In all six case studies, **tertiary education institutions and dedicated training infrastructures** play a central role in the cluster’s functioning, in ways that differ across cases but consistently emerge as

analytically important. In Dundee, **AU University** is one of the two anchor institutions of the cluster (alongside the legacy of DMA Design), and it operates as a specialised game-design hub with international reputation. In Turin, the cluster relies on a mix of public (Università di Torino, Politecnico, IAAD) and private (notably Event Horizon School) institutions, with a debate on the saturation of the talent pool – too many graduates for the absorption capacity of the cluster – and on the alignment between curricula and industry needs. In Brno, the Game_Cluster has been instrumental in shaping the local educational ecosystem, contributing to the foundation of the secondary game-design school (2021) and to the game-art programmes at the universities. In Fundão, the educational dimension was structurally integrated into the Innovation Plan from the start – the Coding Academy, the Game Lab Fundão, the articulation between high school, university and professional schools all reflect the same logic. In Lyon, the École Émile Cohl is one of the oldest training institutions in the French video game industry, and Gamagora plays a comparable role for executive training. In Bordeaux, ENJMIN (founded 2003) is the most important national public school in the field.

What varies across cases is the **balance between public and private institutions**, the **degree of integration with the local game industry**, the **specialisation level** (dedicated game programmes vs general computer science / arts), and the **anchoring institution effect** (a single dominant institution shapes the cluster’s identity in Dundee, while Turin combines multiple institutions in a less centralised configuration). These variations are themselves candidate dimensions for the typology.

4.1.3. Tension between artistic / creativity-driven identity and business / scaling logic

A third pattern, recurrent in several cases, concerns the **tension between an artistic or creativity-driven identity of the cluster and a business or scaling logic**. The tension is articulated most explicitly in the Turin and Lyon cases. In Turin, respondents repeatedly described the local cluster as oriented toward **quality- and creativity-driven productions** rather than toward commercial scaling – one respondent’s description of Turin developers as “the punks of the industry” captures the posture and is associated with an explicit reluctance to chase mainstream success on its own terms. In Lyon, the legacy of Infogrames and of the “French touch” of the 1980s–1990s has anchored an **auteur-oriented identity** that several mature studios (Arkane, Artefacts) carry forward as a deliberate strategic choice; the cluster is described as a space where “artistic integrity over purely commercial logic” coexists with the necessity to mobilise public and private funding.

The tension also appears, in different forms, in Brno (where the GameC_luster’s debate on the lobbying role and on more public visibility is framed against the value of informal voluntarism), in Dundee (where the local actors’ identity is described as one of “doing their own thing” in opposition to mainstream industry expectations), and in Fundão (where the cluster’s distinctive value is associated with quality-of-life and human-centred values rather than with commercial volume).

4.1.4. Crises as positive catalysts for collective action

A fourth pattern concerns the **role of crises as positive catalysts for collective action and cluster structuration**. The pattern can be traced across nearly all six cases:

- in **Lyon**, the Infogrames crisis of 1997 triggered the spin-off wave that became the seed of the contemporary cluster; subsequent crises (the 2001–2003 international shock, the end of Imaginove around 2018, the current sectoral crisis in the French industry) have repeatedly served as catalysts for the structuration and the institutional reconfiguration of collective action;
- in **Bordeaux**, the Kalisto collapse of 2002 produced the empirically paradigmatic case: a cluster recreated almost from scratch through the mobilisation of mobile resources (Kalisto alumni, IPs, personal ties) over the 2002–2007 transition phase, leading to the foundation of SoGames in 2007;
- in **Brno**, the 2024 audiovisual law lobbying episode functioned as a catalyst that transformed the Game_Cluster from a primarily local-regional informal association into a national-scale lobbying actor, with consequences that the cluster is still processing internally;
- in **Fundão**, the post-2010 Portuguese financial crisis (“Troika” period) was the moment in which the Innovation Plan emerged as a strategic response by the municipality, with the tech sector and later the video games as one of its pillars;
- in **Turin**, the pattern is less pronounced because the cluster is younger and has not yet faced a structuring crisis, but the discussion at BM #5 suggested that the relative absence of crisis may itself be a discriminating feature.

This pattern is one of the most analytically dense patterns in the corpus, and it will be a structural input to the typology work in **D3.3**.

4.1.5. The persistent demand for political and public recognition

The fifth pattern concerns the **demand by cluster actors for political, institutional and public recognition** – a demand that recurs in all six cases, in different forms but with consistent salience. In Turin, the demand is articulated as the recurring narrative of “we need a hit” – a flagship product that would propel the cluster to the same recognition level as the established cultural sectors of the city (notably cinema). In Dundee, the demand surfaces in the discussion of the absence of local council recognition despite the existence of national-level tax credits (BM #4 / BM #5 discussion with Darshana Jayemanne). In Brno, the demand has been partly answered by the audiovisual law lobbying success, but the discussion of “external communication” and “visibility” continues to structure the Game_Cluster’s internal debates. In Fundão, the demand has been embedded into the Innovation Plan itself, but the broader Portuguese national context still treats video games as a marginal sector. In Lyon and Bordeaux, the demand is articulated through the formalised relations with two ministries (Economy and Culture) and through the constant negotiation with the *pôle de compétitivité* and the CNC support mechanisms – but the underlying narrative of “we are not sufficiently recognised” remains consistent across interviews.

The demand for recognition takes different forms across cases – institutional, political, public, financial – and is differently structured by the national context (centralised in France, decentralised in Italy, regionally-driven in the Czech Republic, EU-shaped in Portugal). These variations are themselves candidate axes of differentiation for the typology.

4.2. Four discriminating dimensions across the cases

In counterpoint to the five convergent patterns, the cross-cluster work has identified four dimensions along which the six cases **differ in analytically meaningful ways**. These dimensions are candidate axes for the typology, although the typology itself will combine them in ways that **D3.3** will determine.

4.2.1. Trajectory of emergence: bottom-up community vs top-down policy

The clusters differ markedly in the **structural logic of their emergence**. Three pure types and one hybrid type can be identified:

- **Bottom-up community-driven emergence** – the cluster emerges from the activity of individual actors (developers, students, hobbyists, informal communities), with public institutions joining at a later stage as supporters. This is paradigmatically the case of Dundee, Turin, and to a substantial extent Brno (where the informal community pre-existed the formalisation as Game_Cluster).
- **Top-down policy-driven emergence** – the cluster is initiated by a public actor (typically the municipality), with the private actors aligning subsequently. Fundão is the paradigmatic case: the Innovation Plan of 2012 is explicitly the founding event of the cluster, and the municipality remains today its dominant initiating actor, with an explicit ambition to gradually detach itself as the community matures.
- **Anchor-firm-driven emergence** – the cluster emerges from the legacy of a single major firm whose presence shapes the conditions for subsequent spin-offs and structuration. This is the case of Lyon (Infogrames) and Bordeaux (Callisto), although in both French cases the anchor firm has collapsed and the cluster has reconstructed itself on the legacy.
- **Hybrid emergence** – combinations of the above. The Lyon and Bordeaux cases combine the anchor-firm logic with substantial public support from the French decentralised system; Dundee combines a bottom-up community emergence with the anchor-institution role of AU University.

The classification is provisional. It will be refined in **D3.3** through the causal analysis of each case.

4.2.2. Degree of formalisation: a continuum

The six clusters can be positioned along a **continuum of formalisation**, from purely informal coordination to fully formalised cluster organisations:

- **Purely informal pole:** Dundee – no formal cluster organisation, coordination through AU University, informal events, and personal networks.
- **Active resistance to formalisation:** Turin – informal network with limited institutionalisation (T-Union and the local IGDA chapter), explicit reluctance among respondents to use the term *cluster* or to formalise membership structures.
- **Formalisation in active progress:** Brno – informal community institutionalised as the Game_Cluster, with ongoing internal debates on membership fees, on the lobbying role, and

on the boundary between the cluster as research object and the Game_Cluster as organisation. The Brno case is in an active transition.

- **Hybrid mid-position:** Fundão – formal coordination through the municipality and the incubator structures, with an explicit detachment ambition; no formal cluster association of game studios as yet, but the institutional architecture is in place.
- **Fully formalised pole:** Lyon (Game-Only) and Bordeaux (SoGames) – formal cluster associations with hybrid democratic-professional governance, paid permanent staff, structured programmes, formal membership criteria, and dense articulation with public funding mechanisms.

This continuum was first explicitly mapped by Chahira Mehouchi during BM #4 (Fundão) and BM #5 (Lyon) and has been one of the most stable framing devices of the cross-cluster discussion. It is highly likely to be one of the axes of the typology in **D3.3**.

4.2.3. Presence and role of an anchor firm or anchor institution

The third dimension concerns the **presence and the role of an anchor firm or anchor institution** in the cluster’s history and current functioning. Four configurations can be distinguished:

- **Anchor firm with subsequent legacy** – the cluster emerged from a major firm whose collapse left a tissue of alumni, IPs, and personal ties that incubated the subsequent ecosystem. Lyon (Infogrames) and Bordeaux (Callisto) are the paradigmatic cases. The legacy operates as a continuing structuring force decades after the anchor firm’s transformation or disappearance.
- **Anchor institution rather than anchor firm** – the cluster is structured around a major institutional actor (typically a university or a public agency) rather than around a firm. Dundee fits this pattern, with AU University playing the anchor role alongside the historical DMA Design legacy. The institutional anchor provides the talent pipeline, the reputational anchor, and the continuity that the firm anchor provides in the French cases.
- **No anchor firm or institution** – the cluster has no single founding actor that operates as anchor, and it is structured by a more distributed set of contributing actors. Turin, Brno and Fundão fit this pattern in different ways. In Turin, the four founding studios of 2013–2014 form a distributed founding core; in Brno, the Game_Cluster itself plays a coordinating but not anchoring role; in Fundão, the municipality plays an initiating role but its ambition is precisely to phase out that anchoring function.
- **Public initiator as anchor** – a borderline case where the anchor is a public actor (typically the municipality) rather than a firm or an institution in the academic sense. Fundão can be read this way, with the municipality functioning as the anchor for the proto-cluster phase.

The configuration of the anchor (firm, institution, public actor, none) is hypothesised to be one of the major axes of the typology – and one that articulates with the trajectory of emergence (Section 4.2.1).

4.2.4. Articulation with the national context

The fourth dimension concerns the **articulation of the cluster with the national context** – the degree to which the cluster operates as an embedded element of a structured national industry, or as an isolated local phenomenon. Four configurations can be identified:

- **Strong national articulation through decentralised support** – France (Lyon and Bordeaux). The cluster is articulated with the SNJV national syndicate, with a network of eight regional cluster associations, with two ministerial supervisions, with the CNC, and with national-scale programmes (France 2030). The decentralised French model gives substantial weight to the regional and metropolitan levels in resource allocation.
- **Emerging national articulation** – Brno. The cluster operated primarily at the regional level until the 2024 audiovisual law lobbying episode, which made it a visible national actor. The articulation is recent and is the object of internal debate.
- **National-international articulation with weak local-national link** – Dundee. The cluster benefits from national-scale tax credits but suffers from limited local council recognition; its primary external articulation is with the international video game industry (AU’s international reputation, the tax-credit-driven attraction of international studios).
- **Weak national articulation** – Turin and Fundão. In Turin, the national IIDEA association exists but is described as not particularly present in Turin; the cluster is largely invisible at national level. In Fundão, the national video game sector is itself emerging, and the cluster operates more in articulation with European programmes (such as **GAME-ER** itself) than within a structured national industry.

The articulation with the national context interacts with all the other dimensions and will need to be treated carefully in the typology – possibly as a contextual modifier rather than as a primary axis.

5. FROM FACILITATION TO TYPOLOGY

The fourth and final key stage of the **T3.2** facilitation work – **November 2025 to May 2026** – consisted in translating the methodological refinements of the previous stages into an operational architecture for the next deliverable. The translation was the object of three meetings that should be read as a sequence: **BM #6 (Bordeaux, 26 November 2025)**, where the structure of **D3.3** was first proposed; **BM #7 (transversal, 24 February 2026)**, where the methodology and the labour division were operationalised; and the **WP2-D3 working session (19 May 2026)**, where the integration with the regional spatial analysis was settled. The present section consolidates the outputs of this sequence and formalises the handover from **T3.2** to **T3.3**.

6. CONCLUSIONS

D3.2 has documented the methodological journey of WP3 between two milestones: the delivery of the consolidated analytical grid in **D3.1** (M8) and the forthcoming production of the cross-cluster typology in **D3.3** (M29). Through the work of the case study steering committee, it has shown how a paper grid became a living analytical practice, how that practice matured through successive conceptual moves, and how it progressively gave shape to a workable comparative framework. Three contributions of the deliverable deserve to be underlined:

- First, the case study steering committee produced a genuine analytical toolkit, not merely a coordination space. The seven bi-monthly meetings and the two working sessions generated a sequence of conceptual refinements, namely the static/processual distinction, the organisation/organising distinction, the dismantling of "membership" into more workable concepts, the integration of Boschma's proximity grid, and the causality-based methodological turn that go well beyond what was available in **D3.1**. This toolkit is now operational both for **D3.3** and for the wider research community working on video game clusters.
- Second, the cross-cluster dialogue identified five convergent patterns and four discriminating dimensions that are robust enough to inform the typology construction without pre-empting it. These provide **D3.3** with a structured entry point: the typology can be built not from scratch on the totality of the WP4 material, but on a set of dimensions that have already been collectively identified as analytically discriminating across the six cases.
- Third, the full methodological architecture for **D3.3** has been collectively agreed upon and operationalised. This collective agreement, reached through BM #6 (November 2025), BM #7 (February 2026), and the WP2-D3 session (May 2026), is itself one of the most significant outputs of T3.2.

Looking back, the facilitation work documented in this deliverable has produced three kinds of value worth retaining for future projects of comparable scope. It has demonstrated that the cumulative refinement of an analytical grid through structured peer dialogue is methodologically productive and arguably more robust than its alternative, where each team codes in isolation using a fixed grid. It has shown that initiating the cross-cluster dialogue well before the formal start of **T3.3** makes genuine comparison possible, avoiding the classical pitfall of large comparative projects in which multiple monographs are produced but cannot be synthesised because each team has framed its case in incompatible terms. Finally, and more intangibly, the seven meetings have built between the five teams a shared analytical vocabulary, a shared sense of the field, and a working trust that will be essential during the more demanding phases of **T3.3** and the recommendations deliverable. These are the conditions under which a multi-partner consortium can deliver a typology rather than a stack of reports.

REFERENCES

- Boschma, Ron. 2005. "Proximity and Innovation: A Critical Assessment." *Regional Studies* 39 (1): 61–74. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0034340052000320887>.
- Crozier, Michel, and Erhard Friedberg. 1977. *L'acteur et le système : les contraintes de l'action collective*. Paris: Seuil. [English edition: *Actors and Systems: The Politics of Collective Action*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980.]
- Gherardi, Silvia. 2006. *Organizational Knowledge: The Texture of Workplace Learning*. Oxford: Blackwell.
- Gherardi, Silvia, and Antonio Strati. 2012. *Learning and Knowing in Practice-Based Studies*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar.
- Langley, Ann. 1999. "Strategies for Theorizing from Process Data." *Academy of Management Review* 24 (4): 691–710. <https://doi.org/10.5465/amr.1999.2553248>.
- Ragin, Charles C. 1987. *The Comparative Method: Moving Beyond Qualitative and Quantitative Strategies*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Ragin, Charles C. 2008. *Redesigning Social Inquiry: Fuzzy Sets and Beyond*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.
- Rihoux, Benoît, and Charles C. Ragin, eds. 2009. *Configurational Comparative Methods: Qualitative Comparative Analysis (QCA) and Related Techniques*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Schneider, Carsten Q., and Claudius Wagemann. 2012. *Set-Theoretic Methods for the Social Sciences: A Guide to Qualitative Comparative Analysis*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

GAME-ER deliverables cited in this report

- GAME-ER Consortium. D2.2 — Analysis of the spatial distribution of the video game industry in Europe. UNITO. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19351255>
- GAME-ER Consortium. D2.3 — Report and Mapping of video game clusters across European regions. UNITO.
- GAME-ER Consortium. D3.1 — Analysis grid and interview script. CRG. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17542326>
- GAME-ER Consortium. D4.1 — Report on Primary Data Collection <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17535331>
- GAME-ER Consortium. D4.2 — Report on documents analysis. AU
- GAME-ER Consortium. D4.3 — Historical Development of Clusters. UNITO.
- GAME-ER Consortium. D4.4 — Mapping of Actors. CUNI.
- GAME-ER Consortium. D4.5 — Mapping of skills. AU

ANNEX A – SYNTHESIS OF THE BI-MONTHLY MEETINGS (MEETING MINUTES)

This annex provides a structured synthesis of each of the seven bi-monthly meetings and of the two methodological working sessions held during **T3.2**. Each synthesis follows a common "meeting minutes" format and focuses on what was learned about **the methodology and the comparative framework** — these are not cluster reports (cluster reports are in WP4 deliverables **D4.1**, **D4.2** and **D4.3**).

A.1 Bi-monthly Meeting #1 – Dundee (AU), 17 December 2024

Format	online (Zoom), 1h31.
Presenting team	AU University (Stefano De Paoli, Jose David Gómez-Urrego, Darshana Jayemanne, with team members Anastasia Akinina, Beatrix Livesey-Stephens, Martin Lynagh, Geoffrey Marmonier).
Other participants	CRG, UNITO, CUNI, INOVA+, OGR, and SPIN.
Agenda	(i) advances on the Dundee cluster analysis — main characteristics and timeline of development; (ii) reflections on the analytical grid and its use; (iii) next steps.
Major discussed points	The AU team presented the reconstruction of major events, factors and phases that marked the emergence of the Dundee cluster until the beginning of the 2000s. The presentation emphasised the informal structure and functioning of the cluster, the main factors that have influenced its development, the features of its collaboration structure, the key players and stakeholders (notably DMA Design and AU University), and the major strengths and challenges encountered by the cluster.
Methodological inputs	The team presented the methodological approach adopted for the analysis: inductive coding performed in NVivo, with an iterative process of testing and adjusting the codes; a stable version then mapped onto the WP3 analytical grid. Two coding approaches were run in parallel — manual coding with NVivo support, and AI-assisted coding — with the two approaches reportedly converging. The codebook produced 54 codes organised in four hierarchical levels (large codes, codes, simplified codes, definitions).
Feedback on the grid	The first systematic feedback on the D3.1 grid was articulated. The team identified four categories as most useful — Social context and cultural influences, Collaboration and networks, Circulation of people, Performance of collective activities — and five categories as less useful — Industrial structure, Strategy and leadership, Management and execution, Governance efficiency,

	Membership changes and performance. The team proposed four additions to the grid: Future of the cluster, Legacy of the cluster, Complementary services as a new category of stakeholders, Space of independent organisations and collectives. Several redundancies and similarities among categories were identified that could allow simplification of the coding grid.
Cross-cluster resonances	The discussion raised the question of whether the "less useful" categories were genuinely weak or whether they reflected the structural feature of an informal cluster (which would resurface as a major analytical question at BM #2 and WS #4). Other dimensions identified as candidates for future comparison included emergence and mode of development (formal vs organic), demography of companies composing the cluster, main resources provided by the cluster, main factors of attractiveness (volume, dynamics, creativity), and key success factors. The relevance of the timeline as a first tool to understand and map the development of a cluster was explicitly noted in the meeting minutes — a proposition that has been retained as a methodological convention across all subsequent meetings (Section 3.4).
Next steps decided	The AU team would continue with the mapping of remaining codes onto the WP3 grid, the coding of remaining interviews, and the refinement of the timeline. A dedicated working session was planned for January 2025 (eventually held on 7 March 2025 as Working Session #4) between the AU and CRG teams to better discuss the definition of the categories and the integration of the Dundee material into the analytical grid. The choice of the next cluster to be presented was deferred.

A.2 Bi-monthly Meeting #2 – Turin (UNITO), 24 February 2025

Format	online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Presenting team	UNITO (Nicola Costalunga, Riccardo Fassone, Cecilia Maronero).
Other participants	Chahira Mehouchi (CRG), Thomas Paris (CRG), Stefano De Paoli (AU), Jose David Gómez-Urrego (AU), Darshana Jayemanne (AU), Jan Švelch (CUNI), Luis Leça (INOVA+).
Agenda	(i) presentation of the Turin cluster, its history, structure and dynamics; (ii) Turin codebook and its mapping onto the WP3 grid; (iii) reflections on the analytical grid; (iv) cross-cluster discussion.

Major discussed points	<p>The UNITO team presented the Turin cluster as a community of approximately 30 active studios, characterised by its informal nature and the resistance of local actors to the term cluster (with preference for ecosystem, network or scene). The team articulated a tentative timeline structured around three key periods: the pre-cluster period (from 2000, with the Virtuality Conference and early studios); the founding phase (2013–2014, the "year zero" with the consolidation of four founding studios); and the maturation phase (from 2020, with the first IGDA Italy chapter and the recent QuickLoad accelerator-driven second wave around 2022).</p>
Methodological inputs	<p>The team presented the codebook structure: 4 themes / 27 codes / 83 sub-codes, with definitions consolidated through an iterative process. The codebook was constructed semi-inductively — initial codes emerged from the data and were then mapped onto the WP3 grid. The team reported a productive but imperfect overlap between the inductive codes and the grid categories. The codebook was produced in NVivo in two versions (Italian, then English with extracts kept in Italian).</p>
Feedback on the grid	<p>The UNITO feedback converged substantially with the AU feedback from BM #1. Categories most useful: Influencing factors, Cluster features and components, Cluster dynamics. Categories less useful: Strategy and leadership, Management and execution, Membership and stakeholder changes. The team noted the absence of categories on the performance of the cluster as such. The UNITO team also proposed the addition of an entry mechanisms sub-code under Cluster dynamics, capturing the mechanisms through which new firms and actors enter the core network of the cluster (Section 3.5).</p>
Cross-cluster resonances	<p>The convergence of the "less useful" categories between Dundee and Turin became analytically visible. Nicola Costalunga formulated what proved to be a foundational interpretive move: "some of your most useful categories and our least useful ones are the same categories, but it is something related to the very structure of the differences of our clusters" — a structural reading of the divergence that reframed the methodological debate and that was carried forward into Working Session #4. The discussion also raised the question of the artistic-vs-business tension in the cluster (Turin developers described as "the punks of the industry"), and the role of tertiary education in the cluster (mix of public and private institutions, with debate on the saturation of the talent pool).</p>
Next steps decided	<p>A dedicated working session would be organised in early March to consolidate the cross-cluster feedback on the grid (this became Working Session #4). The</p>

	choice of the next presenting team was provisionally identified as CUNI for the Brno cluster.
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A.3 Working Session #4 — grid refinement (AU + UNITO + CRG), 7 March 2025

Format	online (Zoom), approximately one hour.
Participants	Chahira Mehouchi (CRG), Thomas Paris (CRG), Stefano De Paoli (AU), Jose David Gómez-Urrego (AU), Darshana Jayemanne (AU), Nicola Costalunga (UNITO), Cecilia Maronero (UNITO).
Status	working session — not a bi-monthly meeting. Dedicated methodological session to consolidate the feedback received during BM #1 (Dundee) and BM #2 (Turin) on the WP3 analytical grid, in preparation for the systematic deployment of the refined grid on the four remaining case studies.
Agenda	(i) consolidation of the useful / less-useful / additional categories identified by the AU and UNITO teams; (ii) discussion of the underlying conceptual issues (formal vs informal, static vs longitudinal); (iii) operational implications for the grid and the codebooks; (iv) preparation of the next bi-monthly meeting (Brno).
Major discussed points and methodological inputs	<p>Working Session #4 produced six conceptual moves that constitute the methodological backbone of the toolkit, documented in detail in Section 3.2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • structural reading of the useful / less-useful divergence — the "less useful" categories of the grid reflect the formal-organisation bias of the original grid, not its analytical weakness; informal clusters require a reframing rather than a discarding of these categories; • static / processual reading — proposed by Stefano De Paoli; adding verbs to noun-based categories (e.g. <i>governance</i> → <i>governing</i>) allows the grid to capture processes alongside static configurations; • organisation / organising distinction — proposed by Stefano De Paoli with reference to Silvia Gherardi; endorsed by Thomas Paris with parallel reference to Friedberg and Crozier on formal vs informal organisation; introduces a conceptual vocabulary for the analytical treatment of informal clusters; • three irreducible methodological tensions — formulated by Thomas Paris: ecosystem vs association; holistic vs companies' viewpoint; static vs longitudinal analysis. Each category of the grid must make explicit which side of each tension is being addressed;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dismantling of "membership" — into three more workable concepts: territorial presence, collaboration involvement, sense of belonging. The introduction of <i>sense of belonging</i> as a distinct category was discussed with reservations from Thomas Paris on its subjective character; • integration of Boschma's proximity grid — five proximities (cognitive, organisational, social, institutional, geographical) added as sub-categories under <i>Collaboration features</i>. <p>The session also discussed Ann Langley's temporal bracketing strategy as a methodological reference for combining static and longitudinal analysis on the same case — a reference subsequently mobilised in Section 3.4.3 and Section 3.6.3.</p>
<p>Cross-cluster resonances</p>	<p>The Montreal cluster was repeatedly mobilised in the discussion as a reference case for the question of "sense of belonging without formal membership" (Chahira Mehouchi); a historical Lyon studio founder was mobilised by Thomas Paris as a counter-example of "collaboration without belonging". These cross-references illustrated the analytical productivity of the refined conceptual vocabulary.</p> <p>The session also raised a substantive methodological point articulated by Stefano De Paoli: the grid must work across all WP4 tasks (T4.1 thematic, T4.3 historical, T4.4 actor mapping, T4.5 skills), not only T4.1. Categories that appear under-filled in T4.1 (notably those on actors, networks, skills, and changes over time) may be properly filled by the later WP4 tasks. This insight is carried into Section 2.6 and into the design of the bullet-point template for D3.3 Phase 1.</p> <p>A further methodological caution was raised by Darshana Jayemanne on the question of sampling and power asymmetries: the cases in which "the largest entity in a cluster has not been heard" may produce systematic blind spots in the analysis. This caution is one of the methodological points to be addressed in D3.3.</p> <p>A final cross-cutting remark, articulated by Stefano De Paoli, is that the word "cluster" itself may not capture what is going on in the empirical material. The project's commitment to the term is understood as a communication necessity (notably with the European Commission reviewers), but internally the consortium retains the right to deviate from the term when the empirical situation calls for it (e.g. ecosystem, scene, informal community). This semantic flexibility is one of the substantive outputs of the working session and is reaffirmed in the cross-cluster discussions of BMs #3, #4 and #5.</p>
<p>Next steps decided</p>	<p>The conceptual moves were to be applied by all teams to their codebooks and to be tested on the Brno case at the upcoming BM #3. A short follow-up</p>

	methodological discussion was planned at the physical Brno consortium meeting in late March 2025.
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A.4 Bi-monthly Meeting #3 — Brno (CUNI), 30 April 2025

Format	Format: online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Presenting team	Charles University CUNI (Jan Švelch, Jan Houška, Tereza Fousek Krobová).
Other participants	CRG, AU, UNITO, INOVA+.
Agenda	(i) presentation of the Brno cluster — actors, history, dynamics; (ii) the Game_Cluster organisation and the 2024 audiovisual law episode; (iii) Brno codebook and feedback on the WP3 grid; (iv) cross-cluster discussion.
Major discussed points	The CUNI team presented the Brno cluster around two structuring axes: (i) the Game_Cluster as a formal cluster organisation — founded with an individual-membership model (no fees), governed by a published Ethical Code that values informality and physical presence; and (ii) the 2024 audiovisual law lobbying episode — a national-level lobbying success that transformed the Game_Cluster from a regional informal association into a national-scale actor, with substantial internal consequences. The cluster was described as one in active transition between informal community and formal organisation, with a series of internal debates (membership fees, scope of action, balance between lobbying and informal voluntarism) that constitute the principal current dynamics.
Methodological inputs	The CUNI codebook was structured around the four official goals of the Game_Cluster (educational support, networking, communication, public policy) complemented by a set of inductive codes capturing the cluster's "DNA" (informality, voluntarism, physical presence, ethical code). The team used NVivo with a process broadly comparable to that of UNITO.
Feedback on the grid	The CUNI feedback confirmed the convergences observed at BMs #1 and #2. The reframing of governance to include informal mechanisms (per WS #4) proved operationally tractable on the Brno material. The team also raised a specific terminological challenge: the ambiguity between the Game_Cluster as the local formal organisation and the cluster as the WP3 research object. The Game_Cluster's members do not necessarily think of themselves as part of "a cluster" in the WP3 sense; conversely, several active cluster actors are not

	members of the Game_Cluster. This was articulated as one of the most consequential semantic problems of the project.
Cross-cluster resonances	Stefano De Paoli and Thomas Paris articulated the Game_Cluster / cluster ambiguity as a paradigmatic case of the semantic flexibility discussed at WS #4. The discussion compared the Brno transition with the situation in Lyon (where Game-Only similarly concentrates a formal membership while the broader ecosystem extends beyond it) and with Turin (where no formal cluster organisation exists, but a similar ambiguity operates with respect to T-Union and IGDA Italy). The 2024 audiovisual law episode was also discussed as a candidate instance of the "crisis as catalyst" pattern, in the form of a positive external opportunity rather than a sectoral shock.
Next steps decided	The next bi-monthly meeting was scheduled for July 2025 to present the Fundão case (INOVA+). A short follow-up between the CUNI team and the CRG team was planned to refine the codebook integration with the WP3 grid.

A.5 Bi-monthly Meeting #4 — Fundão (INOVA+), 8 July 2025

Format	online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Presenting team	INOVA+ (Tânia Moreira, Luis Leça).
Other participants	CRG, AU, UNITO, CUNI.
Agenda	(i) presentation of the Fundão proto-cluster; (ii) the Innovation Plan as founding policy event; (iii) Fundão codebook and ChatGPT-assisted coding methodology; (iv) first cross-cluster comparative dialogue.
Major discussed points	The INOVA+ team presented Fundão as a proto-cluster in active formation, structured around the 2012 Municipal Innovation Plan (developed in response to the post-2010 Portuguese financial crisis), the Coding Academy and the Game Lab Fundão, and a small population of game studios in a low-density rural territory. The presentation emphasised the explicit policy-driven nature of the cluster's emergence, the central but transitional role of the municipality, and the explicit ambition of the municipality to gradually phase out its anchoring function as the community matures.

Methodological inputs	The codebook was structured around 18 themes organised in four layers: foundational, strategic, operational, and socio-cultural. The team had used ChatGPT-assisted coding on the 28 interviews conducted (drawing on prompts initially shared by Stefano De Paoli, who had developed a similar approach for AU). The team described in detail the three operational pitfalls of AI-assisted coding (excessive summarisation, data volume limits, fake quotes) and the mitigations adopted (Section 3.3.2). The team also reported on its two-mode experiment (inductive then deductive ChatGPT coding on the same corpus), with the preliminary observation that the inductive codes broadly overlap with the grid but introduce sub-categories that the grid does not anticipate (notably public recognition and socio-cultural barriers).
Cross-cluster resonances	BM #4 marks the explicit shift from cluster-by-cluster presentations to cross-cluster comparative dialogue. Chahira Mehouchi initiated a comparative reading of Fundão against the previously presented cases, identifying three first-order observations: (i) Fundão as the most policy-driven case (top-down emergence) against the more bottom-up trajectories of Dundee, Turin and Brno; (ii) the post-Troika crisis as the founding moment of Fundão's Innovation Plan, consistent with the emerging "crisis as catalyst" pattern; (iii) the central role of education and training (Coding Academy, Game Lab, university articulation) as a structural feature shared with all other cases. The discussion also raised the question of the boundary between a proto-cluster and a cluster — Fundão being explicitly characterised by the team as a proto-cluster — and the analytical treatment of clusters at different stages of structuration.
Next steps decided	The next bi-monthly meeting was scheduled for October 2025 to present the Lyon case (CRG). The cross-cluster dialogue initiated at BM #4 would be continued and deepened across the remaining meetings, leading to the BM #6 (November 2025) discussion on the structure of D3.3.

A.6 Bi-monthly Meeting #5 — Lyon (CRG), 1 October 2025

Format	online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Presenting team	CRG – École Polytechnique (Chahira Mehouchi, Thomas Paris).
Other participants	AU, UNITO, CUNI, INOVA+.
Agenda	(i) presentation of the Lyon cluster — six-phase historical model; (ii) cluster DNA (artistic integrity vs business approach); (iii) multipolar leadership and

	triple typology of services; (iv) cross-cluster comparative dialogue on "crisis as catalyst".
Major discussed points	<p>The CRG team presented the Lyon cluster through a six-phase historical model: (1) foundation with Infogrames (1983–1996); (2) crisis and spin-off wave (1997 onwards, triggered by the Infogrames Bull-Cogema crisis); (3) the Lyon Game association (2002–2005); (4) Imaginove and the institutionalisation leap (2005–2019), articulated with the regional pôle de compétitivité mechanism; (5) the late-Imaginove decline (around 2018–2019); (6) the Game-Only renaissance (2019 onwards). The cluster's DNA was articulated around the tension between artistic integrity and business approach, anchored in the Infogrames legacy and carried forward by mature studios such as Arkane and Artefacts.</p> <p>The presentation also articulated a multipolar leadership configuration: formal leadership through Game-Only's elected board (alternating between major studios), complemented by emblematic individuals whose role transcends their formal position (notably a respected senior figure from the founding generation, mentioned without attribution to preserve interview confidentiality). The cluster's services were characterised through a triple typology: basic services (open to all members), semi-selective services (with admission criteria, e.g. mentor matching), and highly selective services (e.g. the Let's Go programme, accelerator partnerships).</p>
Methodological inputs	The Lyon case was the first to deploy the complete timeline practice (industrial context, main actors, collective action and framework, catalysts across phases) discussed in Section 3.4. The case mobilised approximately 25 interviews and around 130 documents. The CRG team had presented the analytical work on Lyon and Bordeaux at the Rethinking Clusters conference (November 2025), and a paper was submitted to a special issue of the European Management Review.
Cross-cluster resonances	The presentation of Lyon brought to the foreground the "crisis as positive catalyst" pattern, articulated explicitly by Chahira Mehouchi: the 1997 Infogrames crisis was the trigger of the contemporary cluster, and subsequent crises have repeatedly served as catalysts for restructuring. Nicola Costalunga immediately tested the pattern against the Turin case (where the relative absence of crisis may itself be discriminating) and against Brno (where the 2024 audiovisual law operates as a comparable structuring event). The discussion also addressed the legacy effect of an anchor firm: Infogrames as a vanished but structuring presence, comparable to Callisto in Bordeaux and to DMA Design in Dundee. The pattern of the "anchor firm with subsequent legacy" emerged here as a candidate axis of the typology (Section 4.2.3).

	A further substantive discussion concerned the resilience and meta-organisational capacity of the cluster – its capacity to dissolve and reconstruct its formal organisation (Lyon Game → Imaginove → Game-Only) while preserving the underlying organising activity (Section 3.6.3). This was articulated by Chahira Mehouchi as a candidate dimension for the typology, with explicit reference to the organisation/organising distinction of WS #4.
Next steps decided	The next bi-monthly meeting (Bordeaux, November 2025) would mark the transition from cluster presentations to the operational preparation of D3.3.

A.7 Bi-monthly Meeting #6 — Bordeaux (CRG) and D3.3 governance, 26 November 2025

Format	online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Presenting team	CRG – École Polytechnique (Thomas Paris, Chahira Mehouchi).
Other participants	AU, UNITO, CUNI, INOVA+, PNPTC.
Agenda	(i) presentation of the Bordeaux cluster, with focus on the 2002–2007 transition phase; (ii) discussion of the structure of D3.3 (the "baby deliverable" ambition); (iii) labour division and concurrent engineering with D3.4.
Major discussed points	<p>The team presented the Bordeaux case through an analytical entry point deliberately chosen as the most revealing of cluster dynamics: the 2002–2007 transition phase between the Callisto collapse and the foundation of SoGames in 2007. This phase, characterised by an almost-empty starting point, is empirically paradigmatic for the analytical hypothesis that the recreation of an industrial cluster from a collapsed anchor firm is one of the most revealing moments for understanding cluster mechanisms. The presentation traced the mobilisation of mobile resources during this transition — the Callisto alumni network, the residual IPs, the informal personal ties — and the progressive crystallisation of new structures (the early new ventures, the ENJMIN proximity, the eventual formalisation as SoGames).</p> <p>D3.3 governance. The second part of the meeting was dedicated to the operational preparation of D3.3. Thomas Paris proposed a structural shift from cluster-by-cluster work to dimension-by-dimension work, with each WP4 deliverable feeding a corresponding dimensional comparison. The "baby</p>

	<p>deliverable" ambition was formulated: D3.3 should be a concise, dense, ~30–40-page document focused on the typology and its mechanisms, rather than on cluster redescription. The proposition was that the European Commission tends to prefer concise deliverables, and that the redescription of clusters is already in the WP4 deliverables.</p>
Methodological inputs	<p>The session also introduced the "concurrent engineering" principle with D3.4: the bullet points and thematic syntheses produced for D3.3 will simultaneously feed the recommendations work led by PNPTC. The proposition was endorsed by Mariana Viseu on behalf of PNPTC, with the operational consequence that the structure of the recommendations would be shared with the consortium before the physical meeting of March/April 2026.</p>
Cross-cluster resonances	<p>The discussion of the Bordeaux 2002–2007 phase explicitly tested several of the patterns previously identified: (i) the "crisis as catalyst" pattern (the Callisto collapse as the founding crisis); (ii) the "anchor firm with subsequent legacy" pattern (Callisto as vanished but structuring presence); (iii) the role of ENJMIN as an anchor institution rather than as an anchor firm. The pattern of cluster reconstruction from a collapsed anchor emerged as a candidate analytical lens shared by Lyon and Bordeaux, although with different temporal scales.</p> <p>José David Gómez-Urrego raised a substantive point that has been retained as an open methodological question for D3.3: the GAME-ER typology should be constructed in dialogue with existing typologies of media and creative clusters, rather than in isolation. This question is retained as an open question for D3.3 (state-of-the-art section, see Section 5.5).</p>
Next steps decided	<p>The next bi-monthly meeting (BM #7, February 2026) would be the first fully transversal meeting — without a cluster presentation — dedicated to operationalising the D3.3 methodology and the labour division.</p>

A.8 Bi-monthly Meeting #7 — Transversal coordination, 24 February 2026

Format	Format: online (Zoom), approximately 90 minutes.
Participants	Participants: Chahira Mehouchi (CRG), Thomas Paris (CRG), Stefano De Paoli (AU), Jose David Gómez-Urrego (AU), Riccardo Fassone (UNITO), Cecilia Maronero (UNITO), Jan Švelch (CUNI), Luis Leça (INOVA+), and other consortium members.
Status	Status: structurally distinct from the previous bi-monthly meetings — no cluster presentation, fully dedicated to operationalising the D3.3 methodology and labour division. This is the first fully transversal meeting and marks the

	formal transition from T3.2 (facilitation of presentations) to T3.3 (construction of the typology).
Agenda	Agenda: (i) the two-phase process for D3.3; (ii) the causality-based methodology; (iii) labour division and calendar; (iv) integration of WP2 outputs; (v) articulation with D3.4.
Major discussed points and methodological outputs	<p>Major discussed points BM #7 formalised five operational decisions for D3.3, documented in detail in Section 5:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the two-phase process — Phase 1 (cluster bullet points in Excel format) and Phase 2 (thematic syntheses by leaders) — was confirmed; • the causality-based methodology — focusing on micro-mechanisms and configurational causalities rather than statistical regularities — was formally adopted (Section 3.6); • the final labour division was negotiated in real time, with the rebalancing of two dimensions to accommodate UNITO's workload concerns (Riccardo Fassone); the final allocation is documented in Section 5.4; • the calendar was rescheduled, with Phase 1 moved to mid-April 2026 and the typology first draft to early June 2026; • the integration with WP2 outputs was raised as a concern by Riccardo Fassone and Cecilia Maronero — the spatial analysis being at regional level while WP4 is at cluster level — and was deferred to a dedicated working session (which became the 19 May 2026 session). <p>A substantive discussion on the epistemological status of causality with qualitative data was led by José David Gómez-Urrego and Stefano De Paoli, with the position articulated by Thomas Paris that the methodology is anchored in methodological individualism and interpretive social science (not in positivism). The position was endorsed by all participants and is documented in Section 3.6.2.</p> <p>A specific methodological point was raised by Chahira Mehouchi on the evolution of causal links over time — for clusters with substantial temporal depth, the same causal link may operate differently across phases. The phase-bracketed treatment was agreed upon (Section 3.6.3).</p>
Cross-cluster resonances	Cross-cluster resonances. The discussion was structurally less focused on cross-cluster substantive observations (which had been the focus of BMs #4 to #6) and more on the operational architecture of D3.3. The "baby deliverable" ambition was reaffirmed.

Next steps decided	Next steps decided. A dedicated working session with the WP2 lead (Enrico Bertacchini) would be organised to settle the integration of regional and local data; an updated calendar would be circulated; Phase 1 of D3.3 was to be launched with the bullet-point template.
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A.9 WP2 ↔ D3 Working Session — articulation of regional and local data, 19 May 2026

Format	Format: online (Zoom), approximately one hour (in two parts).
Participants	Participants: Chahira Mehouchi (CRG), Thomas Paris (CRG), Enrico Bertacchini (UNITO, WP2 lead).
Status	Status: working session — not a bi-monthly meeting. Dedicated session to settle the integration of WP2 (regional spatial analysis) outputs with the WP3 / WP4 (cluster-level) framework for D3.3, following the question raised at BM #7 by the UNITO team. Note: the session was held in two parts — Part 1 (in scope of D3.2 / D3.3) on WP2 articulation; Part 2 (out of scope) on a future Horizon Europe project. Only Part 1 is reflected in the present synthesis.
Agenda	Agenda: (i) what WP2 outputs are available and at what granularity; (ii) the regional vs cluster-level mismatch; (iii) operational protocol for integration; (iv) calendar implications.
Major discussed points	Major discussed points. Enrico Bertacchini presented the WP2 outputs (D2.2 delivered, D2.3 submitted but not yet published) and articulated their scope: geolocalised maps (region and city level), regional typology of European video game clusters, company-type classification (developer / integrated / publisher / complementary / diversified), longitudinal demography across five time periods, with explicit acknowledgement of the limitations of the MobyGames data (geographic sample representativeness at regional but not necessarily at city level; data fragility in the most recent periods; absence of skills data).
Methodological outputs	The session produced the triangulation principle documented in detail in Section 3.7. The principle was articulated by Enrico Bertacchini: "let us try to understand how we can learn from each other, from the qualitative and the quantitative approach... rather than try to put inside something that is not perfectly compatible." The principle treats the convergences and divergences between WP2 (regional) and WP4 (cluster-level) as themselves analytical material, rather than as a problem to be resolved.

	<p>The session also formalised the operational protocol: CRG formulates a list of comparative questions; UNITO answers from existing WP2 data without launching new analyses; convergences and divergences are integrated into a dedicated section of D3.3 (Section 3.7.3). The paradigmatic example of the productive divergence was articulated by Enrico Bertacchini around Turin and Fundão — both classified as "peripheral scenes" at the regional level but markedly different at the cluster level.</p>
<p>Cross-cluster resonances</p>	<p>The session did not focus on cross-cluster substantive observations, but on the methodological architecture of the WP2 / WP4 articulation. Two priority questions were retained as the first batch for the protocol: comparative demography of clusters, and longitudinal evolution of cluster growth patterns. A third candidate — comparative typology of company types per cluster — was added.</p>
<p>Calendar implications</p>	<p>The session confirmed the extension of D3.3 from end of July 2026 to end of August / mid-September 2026, on Chahira Mehouachi's communication that the workload pressure on parallel WP4 deliverables (D4.4, D4.5) and on the typology integration justified the extension. D3.4 would follow approximately one month later (October 2026 instead of September 2026).</p>
<p>Next steps decided</p>	<p>CRG would send a partial draft of the D3.2 report to UNITO by end of May 2026; the WP2 contribution to D3.3 would be formalised through the protocol agreed at the session; a follow-up session would be organised in summer 2026 if needed.</p>